

D2.3

DAFNE+ use case specifications (final report)

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Abstract

This deliverable presents the final version of the specifications of the DAFNE+ use cases at the end of the second year of the project, that result from their initial specification followed by the first phase of the use cases pilots. The evolutions of the specifications were fed by feedback gathered from target users as they took their first steps on the new DAFNE+ platform, and by progress on the various dimensions of the project - legal, monetisation, DAO/ governance and evaluation. These specifications define the framework and strategy for the second phase of DAFNE+ use case pilots and contribute to the evolution of the next version of the platform.

Keywords

Use case, user feedback, blockchain, NFT, DAO, art, culture, heritage, sound, music, maker, design, open source

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CCI	Cultural and Creative industries
CCPL	Creative commons Public licence
CMS	Content Management System
COALA	Coalition of Automated Legal Applications
DAO	Distributed Autonomous Organisation
DSA	Digital Services Act
EIP	Ethereum Improvement Proposal
EU	European Union
IC3	Institute for Cryptocurrencies and Contracts
IP	Intellectual property
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NFT	Non Fungible Token
NWFA	North West Film Archive
RAVE	Real-time Audio Variational autoEncoder
ToS	Terms of service

UC	Use case
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WYSIWYG	What You See Is What You Get – an expected feature of graphical interfaces

1 Executive summary

This deliverable presents the final version of the specifications of the DAFNE+ use cases at the end of the second year of the project, that result from their initial specification followed by the first phase of the use cases pilots. The evolutions of the specifications were fed by feedback gathered from target users as they took their first steps on the new DAFNE+ platform, and by progress on the various dimensions of the project - legal, monetisation, DAO/ governance and evaluation. These specifications define the framework and strategy for the second phase of DAFNE+ use case pilots and contribute to the evolution of the next version of the platform.

2 Introduction

2.0 Purpose and contents of the document

This deliverable presents the final version of the specifications of the DAFNE+ use cases at the end of the second year of the project, that result from their initial specification documented in deliverable D2.2 followed by the first phase of the use cases pilots presented in deliverable D5.1. It is the outcome of task T2.3 - Use case refinement.

The evolutions of the specifications were fed by feedback gathered from target users as they took their first steps on the new DAFNE+ platform, and by progress on the various dimensions of the project - legal, monetisation, DAO/governance, evaluation and sustainability.

The document starts with chapters dedicated to each of these dimensions that are transversal to all the use cases and the framework they define for the last phase of the use cases pilots, in terms of new possibilities but also potential constraints.

The second part of the document is dedicated to the updated specification of each of the three use cases and their strategy of implementation for their second phase. The organisation of use cases into scenarios proved to be relevant and has been retained. As a reminder, it is structured as follows:

Use case 1 - User generated content at large for heritage (lead: UPM)

Scenario 1.1 - Prosumers in the Cultural Heritage (UPM)

Scenario 1.2 - Students from MMU School of Digital Arts (SODA)

Use case 2 - Experimental sound/music production (lead: IRCAM)

Scenario 2.1 - Creation and use of components (IRCAM)

Scenario 2.2 - Creation and use of work repositories (IRCAM)

Scenario 2.3 - Creation and use of works / private spaces (IRCAM)

Use case 3 - Novel forms of artistic content exploitation (lead: IAAC)

Scenario 3.1 - Repository/Component creator (IAAC)

Scenario 3.2 - Repository/Component user (IAAC)

Scenario 3.3 - Repository/Component contributor (IAAC)

The structure of presentation for of each use case X is the following:

- Introduction
- Description of Scenarios X.Y:
 - Scenario description
 - User profiles
 - Managed assets
 - Promotional materials: *elements needed to present and promote the assets in the marketplace*
 - Conditions for implementation: *requirements on the various project dimensions – platform, legal, monetisation, DAO..*
 - Presentation of user journeys: *succession of stages involving the various stakeholders*
- Implementation strategy: *for the second phase of use case pilots*

These specifications define the framework and strategy for the second phase of DAFNE+ use case pilots and contribute to the evolution of the next version of the platform. The last chapter is dedicated to a synthesis of requirements resulting from the user feedback to feed the specification of the platform update.

2.1 Document structure

- Chapter 3 presents a synthesis of the legal studies carried out, especially on licensing conditions of assets related to NFTs, the framework of Creative Commons adopted for the first use-case phase and

perspectives of evolution of the licensing framework for the second use-case phase based on the NFT Token-Bound license.

- Chapter 4 reminds the situation of the revenue and monetisation framework and identifies the aspects to consider for its evolution, including in its way from tesnet to the mainnet.
- Chapter 5 presents the specification of the DAO to be implemented for the next use-case phase and the identified scenarios for its evolution.
- Chapter 6 presents the evolution of the evaluation framework resulting from its initial specification and last evolutions considering feedback and specificities of each use-case.
- Chapter 7 provides first elements of analysis of the conditions necessary for the sustainability of the DAFNE+ platform. It is to be considered as a starting point that will be further elaborated until the end of the project, but it is important to include it already as an important dimension of the last phase of the use-case pilots.
- Chapters 8 to 10 are dedicated to the final specifications of each use-case and their strategy of implementation for their second phase.
- Chapter 11 provides a synthesis of the user requirements for the next platform version
- Chapter 12 concludes the document.

2.2 Dependencies to-from other WPs

This deliverable depends on:

- WP3 and WP4 for the feedback resulting from the existing state of tools and platform
- WP5 for the results of the first use case phase
- WP6 for the legal, governance and monetisation frameworks applicable to all use cases.
- WP7 for the strategy of promotion, user support and community management.

It provides valuable information to:

- WP3 for the evaluation framework of the tools

-
- WP4 for use case requirements on the next platform version
 - WP5 for the specification of the second phase of use case pilots
 - WP6 for use case feedback on legal, governance and monetisation aspects
 - WP7 for the strategy of dissemination, user support and community management for each use case community

3 Legal aspects and licensing conditions

3.0 Introduction

From a purely technical perspective, NFTs are digitally scarce and non-fungible (unique and non-divisible) cryptographic tokens recorded on the blockchain (a distributed ledger).^[1] However, there is significant dissonance between the claims and promises of NFTs in technical environments and the reality of what NFTs actually represent from a legal point of view and in particular the rights that NFT's "ownership" grants in relation to copyright.^[2] NFTs simply consist in metadata written on the blockchain through a smart contract (computer code executing if-then conditions).^[3] The metadata contains information regarding a digital object's location^[4] and links to it.^[5] From a legal perspective it is thus widely recognised that an NFT is inherently distinct from the asset it references and any IP rights in it.^[6] Therefore, an NFT alone does not create or transfer any rights in the linked asset.^[7] In the legal scholarship it is common to represent that intellectual property distinguishes the protectable intangible asset (*corpus mysticum*) from its physical representation (*corpus mechanicum*).^[8] In the case of NFTs it seems clear that the "ownership" of the token is separate from any exclusive rights over the linked work of authorship itself.^[9] The very same determination of whether an NFT can be "owned" in the traditional legal sense of the word is object of debate.^[10] NFT purchasers will thus not inherently have a right to freely use the IP protected works and will require authorisation from the relevant copyright holder if protected by IP rights.^[11] After all, this is not too different from the purchase of a book. Unless it comes with an additional copyright licence, the acquirer of a copy of a book does not receive any additional copyright in it, therefore, if he reproduces or recite the book in public, absent other legal basis, he will commit a copyright infringement.^[12] In the case of an NFT the issue is further complicated by the fact that the NFT does (almost never) not embed the work, but simply information about the work.^[13]

^[1] EU Blockchain Observatory, *Demistifying Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs)*, (2023) pp.4-7

^[2] Andres Guadamuz, 'The treachery of images: non-fungible tokens and copyright', *Journal of Intellectual Property Law & Practice* (2021), pp.2-6; Balázs Bodó, Alexandra Giannopoulou, Péter Mezei and Joao Pedro Quintais: 'The Rise of NFTs: These Aren't the Droids You're Looking For', *EIPR*, 44 (5) (2022) pp. 268-283

^[3] EU Blockchain Observatory (n1) pp4-7; Guadamuz 2021 (n2); Bodó et al 2022 (n2)

^[4] While including the digital asset in the metadata itself is possible from a purely technical perspective, it is extremely uncommon due to the inefficiency resulting from elevated gas fees. See Michael M Murray, 'NFT Ownership and Copyrights', *Indiana Law Review* 56 (2023) pp.371-2

^[5] EU Blockchain Observatory (n1) pp4-7; Guadamuz 2021 (n2); Bodó et al 2022 (n2)

^[6] Guadamuz 2021 (n2); Bodó et al 2022 (n2); Murray 2023 (n4)

^[7] Ibid

^[8] Lionel Bently et al, *Intellectual Property Law* (6th edn, OUP 2022)pp.3-5; Opinion of the Advocate General of the Court of Justice of 09 July 2015, (ECLI:EU:C:2015:461) [37] available at <https://e-justice.europa.eu/ecli/ECLI:EU:C:2015:461>

^[9] Guadamuz 2021 (n2); Bodó et al 2022 (n2); Murray 2023 (n4)

^[10] Sjef van Erp, 'Ownership of digital assets?', *European Property Law Journal*, 5(2) (2016) 73-76;

^[11] Guadamuz 2021 (n2); Bodó et al 2022 (n2); Murray 2023 (n4)

^[12] Ibid

^[13] Ibid

Copyright, licensing and NFTs in the DAFNE+ platform

The separation between NFT ownership and any legal right to the underlying asset is precisely **the core challenge for IP licensing on the DAFNE+ platform**. The DAFNE+ platform aims to allow creators to license their works through NFTs, so that an NFT buyer will receive certain pre-established rights by purchasing an NFT on the marketplace. As the sale of an NFT alone does not convey any rights, establishing a way to bind and align the NFT with IP rights in the linked work is necessary to facilitate the execution of the DAFNE+ model. The license must remain attached to the token throughout downstream sales, as the DAFNE+ model and user's legal certainty would be undermined if at any moment a user could decide to no longer license the linked work's IP rights with the NFT.

Rights to an NFT's linked IP asset can be conveyed through additional contractual agreements fulfilling applicable law requirements.^[1] These can be individually negotiated between buyer and seller or included in contracts of adhesion in a platform's Terms of Service (ToS).^[2] While being able to effectively convey IP rights in the initial sale, both approaches raise legal validity concerns in downstream sales, particularly when conducted across marketplaces. NFT licenses included in ToS do not attach to the NFT itself and are only valid on the initial platform and subject to a user's assent (which must fulfil applicable law requirements).^[3] Any sales across marketplaces outside the platform will not necessarily be subject to such terms absent the buyer's explicit acceptance of the initial ToS.^[4] The validity of the license thus ultimately solely relies on a secondary buyer's willingness to accept and comply with such initial agreement, further complicated by the fact that marketplaces may not be aware of, be able to display or have the ability to facilitate the execution of such initial agreement.^[5] Including a license in a platform's ToS thus does not guarantee the license follows the NFTs across every sale outside the platforms. Individual contractual agreements between an NFT buyer and seller are equally inadequate in guaranteeing that the IP license follows the NFT across each downstream sale. A contract only binds parties who intend to be bound and reach sufficient agreement.^[6] Therefore, while a contractual agreement can adequately license or transfer IP rights between two users in an initial transaction, it is difficult to imagine an effective duty or obligation to transfer/license the underlying work's IP rights with the NFT can be imposed on any subsequent NFT sellers/buyers. There are two different

levels of transaction, one relating to the parties to a contract for the IP in a work and one relating to the parties in a contract for an NFT. Maintaining these two levels aligned and dependant from each-other, particularly after the initial transfer, is the difficulty that, from a legal point of view, many platforms have tried to address, quite unsuccessfully due to the legal considerations summarised above. Contracts can be of assistance but only up to a certain point.

Arguably contracts could adequately limit issues in secondary sales if operating in a closed platform environment, where each user is vetted, accepts the platform ToS and the NFTs and linked works are solely available and accessible on the platform. Implementing a closed platform however frustrates the idea of a distributed ledger and governance model central to the DAFNE+ project, imposing a degree of control and centralisation that is incompatible with the envisioned platform model. Coding the license terms in the NFT metadata, either by including the license text or a link to the license document^[7], has been presented as a possible solution.^[8] While arguably addressing the license communication issues to secondary buyers, its legal validity is equally contentious. A license in NFT metadata could in theory sufficiently clarify the licensing conditions of the NFT metadata itself in which it is included. However, as from a legal perspective the NFT and its metadata are distinct from the linked asset and its IP, it remains unclear whether it can alone constitute a valid license to the underlying work's IP and how such a license would be enforced and transferred in secondary sales. As highlighted by Odinet and Moringello, the execution and implementation of licenses in metadata both from a legal and technical perspective depends on speculative extant technology.^[9]

The fundamental challenge in NFT IP licensing on DAFNE+ thus ultimately lies in establishing a valid mechanism that can bind the NFT to the linked asset's IP to ensure legal and enforceable rights that can follow the NFT through secondary sales. Such an endeavour is complicated by the unregistered nature of copyright, conflicting starkly with the registered nature of blockchain. An IP holder may in fact freely transfer and license the rights to the underlying work's IP. Due to the unregistered nature of copyright, tracking IP ownership and licenses may be complex. This could lead to a dissociation between the NFT and linked work's license, generating significant confusion regarding who owns the relevant rights or even double-transfers of

rights.^[10] Blockchain is unable to address or prevent off-chain transfers, thus failing to guarantee a reliable certificate of IP ownership.^[11]

An additional obstacle in the DAFNE+ model concerns compatibility in derivative works' licenses. Such an issue is not exclusive to NFTs but rather is a common concern across licensing.^[12] When multiple works under distinct licenses are combined to create a new derivative, the resulting work's license need be compatible with the initial works' licensing conditions.^[13] While the compatibility analysis of different licenses requires an individual assessment, DAFNE+ aims to automate license compatibility in order to simplify license selection for users and reduce the possibility of error. A limited set of standardised licenses, with a uniform and predefined set of terms (particularly in regard to liability, territorial, temporal scopes) could address such an issue by promoting compatibility and facilitating the assessment.

It should finally be noted that, despite the widespread emergence and availability of NFT marketplaces, there is little legal certainty regarding their operations and NFT transactions.^[14] Platforms' NFT licensing terms (when provided) often are not clearly communicated to users, have an uncertain legal basis and lack interoperability in sales across marketplaces.^[15] Further insights into existing NFT marketplaces models and their IP ownership and licensing terms will be provided as part of D6.1.

^[1] Michael D Murray, 'Transfers and Licensing of Copyrights to NFT Purchasers', *Stanford Journal of Blockchain Law & Policy* (2023) Available at <https://stanford-jblp.pubpub.org/pub/copyrights-nft-purchasers>;

^[2] Murray 2023 (n1); Bodó et al 2022 (n2), 6-15

^[3] Ibid

^[4] Ibid

^[5] Ibid

^[6] Art 2:101 PECL

^[7] Including a link to the license rather than the entire text in the metadata would be preferable to avoid elevated gas fees. See Murray 2023 (n1)

^[8] See Diana Stern, Dazza Greenwood and Bryan Wilson, 'NFT Legal & Licensing Integration'. *MIT Computational Law Report* (2021) Available at: <https://law.mit.edu/pub/ideaflow6>; Murray 2023 (n1)

^[9] Juliet M Moringiello and Christopher K.Odinet, 'The Property Law of Tokens' *74 Florida Law Review* (2022), 641 at note 230

^[10] USPTO, *Non-Fungible Tokens and Intellectual Property. A report to congress.* (2024), 25

^[11] Alexander Savelyev, 'Copyright in the blockchain era: promises and challenges', *Comput Law Secur Rev* 34 (2018), 550-561; Michèle Finck and Valentina Moscon, 'Copyright Law on Blockchains: Between New Forms of Rights Administration and Digital Rights Management 2.0', *IIC* 50 (2019), 98

^[12] Benjamin Moreau, Patricia Serrano-Alvarado, Matthieu Perrin, Emmanuel Desmontils, 'Modelling the Compatibility of Licenses' In: Hitzler, P., et al. *The Semantic Web. ESWC 2019. Lecture Notes in Computer Science* vol 11503 (2019), 255-7; License Matrix, available at: <https://openminted.github.io/releases/license-matrix/> accessed 14 May 2024

^[13] *ibid*

^[14] Guadamuz 2021 (n2), 11-16

^[15] *Ibid*

3.1 Legal and licensing framework for first use case phase

To address the difficulties identified in NFT licensing, the Creative Commons Public License was selected and suggested for implementation in the initial platform launch. The selected CCPL 4.0 license framework provides the public with a core set of re-use rights (including reproduction, redistribution, performance, communication and making available to the public), conditional on providing attribution to the licensor.^[11] Additional conditions of non-commercial use (NC), no derivative works (ND) and the requirement to share any derivative work under the exact license terms (SA) may be imposed, resulting in 6 possible license options.^[12] By granting a license to the public at large, in what from a EU contract law point of view is akin to a standard form contract, CC licenses can reduce search and information, bargaining, policing and enforcement costs.^[13] The fact that CC licences are public licences, meaning that any member of the public is a potential licensee and has access to the license terms online^[14], has the advantage that the text of the licence is standardised and publicly available with clear versioning.^[15] This contributes to solve the problems of custom licensing, which are licences whose specific wording and clauses changes usually on a per-use basis and where there is no public repository regarding their actual structure and version.^[16]

CC licenses have been selected for implementation in DAFNE+ to facilitate and automate license compatibility in derivative works. The limited set of CC licenses with standardised terms allow for an ex-ante compatibility assessment for each license combination. A CC compatibility chart has been provided for the First Use-Case Phase implementation, highlighting compatible and incompatible license combinations and the necessary resulting licenses for derivative works^[7]. Creative Commons furthermore provides a familiar framework for UC1 and UC3 communities, dedicated to open culture and already utilising such licenses.

As asserted by Creative Commons, due to ownership of the NFT being distinct from ownership of any copyright in the linked work, CC licenses are valid and can be applied to NFTs' underlying works, but obviously no claim is made regarding the work-NFT licence link.^[18] Numerous NFT projects^[19] have already adopted CC to address the copyright challenges associated with NFTS and their underlying works and legal scholarship has recognised the licenses' applicability to an NFTs underlying asset.^[10] CC licenses' public form and

standardised terms can clarify the licensing conditions in an NFTs' **linked work** in a simple and reliable manner which covers all downstream sales, but do not (and cannot) stem from their eventual (and rather infrequent) inclusion in the NFT itself.^[11] While able to clarify licensing conditions in an NFT's linked work, it is thus important to note that CC licenses do not bind the NFT with the linked asset's copyright and related rights. The public nature of the license in fact places NFT holders on equal footing with non-NFT holders, who receive the exact rights to the underlying work without the need to purchase an NFT. CC licenses thus render NFT ownership redundant altogether for licensing purposes.^[12] Arguably, some users may still wish to purchase an NFT to offer creators financial rewards or register an association with an original copy of the work (e.g., "bragging rights").^[13] If the DAFNE+ platform did not centre on NFTs for licensing, the CC framework would be able to address most of the legal challenges identified above. However, as the DAFNE+ business model centres on executing licensing through NFTs, CC licenses alone do not address the business model's primary value proposition.

While CC's open and public nature is suitable for communities committed to open culture such as those in UC1 and UC3, it remains largely incompatible with the needs of UC2. UC2 is characterised by the presence of copyright as well as related rights, whose initial ownership may be fragmented across multiple individuals or entities. Illustratively, the author of a song may hold the relevant copyright rights to license the lyrics or musical work, but the sound recording may be owned by a sound producer and therefore needs to be specifically licensed by this right-holder. Under the CC framework a licensor must represent to own the rights object of the license and only license the rights that they own, thus absent such initial ownership they may not be entitled to certain licensing and activities.^[14] Only creators who own all the rights associated or who have obtained the relevant authorisations will be able to share their works under CC licenses, or any other license, significantly restricting the user base for UC2. UC2's needs to restrict access to content and permissions to create a new work in scenario 2.2 and the creation of private spaces in scenario 2.3 may not necessarily align with CC's open nature, if not in contractually, probably in philosophical terms.

Additionally, in relation to Scenario 2.1 proposing new forms of distribution of software, many assets shared on DAFNE+ may already have been made available on the IRCAM Forum or under other pre-existing licensing

conditions. Accordingly, it would be for right holders to decide whether to relicense their rights under a second licensing scheme, alternative or concurrent to CC (e.g., dual-licensing). On the other hand, the IRCAM Forum license^[15] applying to such assets broadly restricts redistribution and uses to non-commercial purposes.

Following IRCAM's proposal driven by requirements of Scenario 2.2 and after agreement of the partners responsible for the other use cases, CC licensing options have been restricted to **CC BY NC-SA** and **CC BY-NC-ND**. The former allows non-commercial uses and derivative works if licensed under the exact license, while the latter allows for non-commercial uses and no derivative works.^[16]

CC licenses have been suggested and adopted as an initial model to swiftly and easily address the legal issues identified in NFTs, particularly public standard and versioned contracts. Their implementation however puts pressure on the envisioned DAFNE+ model of solely executing licensing through NFTs and Use case 2 workflows. Novel theoretical frameworks that would better fit the DAFNE+ business model and each use case are being explored and evaluated from a legal perspective. It should however be noted that reconciling the platform's decentralised nature with the need for control (monetisation and permissions) presents a significant legal and conceptual challenge associated with developing such new frameworks.

^[1] See Creative Commons, 'About CC licenses' available at: accessed 14 May 2024; Thomas Margoni and Diane Peters, 'Creative Commons Licenses: Empowering Open Access' (March 10, 2016), 4-6 Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2746044>; Michael W Carroll, 'Creative Commons as Conversational Copyright' in Peter K. Yu, ed., Vol. 1, *Intellectual Property and Information Wealth: The issues and practices in the digital age* (2007), 445-61

^[2] Ibid

^[3] See Herkko Hietanen, *The Pursuit of Efficient Copyright Licensing – How Some Rights Reserved Attempts to Solve the Problems of All Rights Reserved*, PhD dissertation, (2008), 51-63

^[4] A human-readable commons deed and a legal code identifying the license terms is provided alongside machine-readable metadata associating the licensed resource's online location with the license's location. See Carroll (n1), 489

^[5] See Hietanen (n3), 535, 96; Margoni and Peters (n2) and Carroll (n2)

^[6] Ibid

^[7] Creative Commons, 'CC and NFTs', available at: <https://creativecommons.org/cc-and-nfts/> Accessed 14 May 2024; .See also Michael D Murray, 'Transfers and Licensing of Copyrights to NFT Purchasers', *Stanford Journal of Blockchain Law & Policy* (2023) Available at <https://stanford-jblp.pubpub.org/pub/copyrights-nft-purchasers;>; Molly Marias, 'I Want My NFT!: How an NFT Creative Commons Parallel Would Promote NFT Viability and Decrease Transaction Costs in NFT Sales', *NYU Journal of Intellectual Property & Entertainment Law* 12:1 (2022) pp.1-35; Marianna Foerg, 'Creative commons and NFTS', *Kluwer Copyright Blog* (2022) available

at:<https://copyrightblog.kluweriplaw.com/2022/10/06/creative-commons-and-nfts-is-cc-licensing-compatible-with-the-new-technologies/>

^[8] E.g. Moonbirds, Nouns, Fidenza, Act of emotion, Mfers, Chain runners, X copy, Cryptoadz

^[9] Murray 2023 (n8); Marias 2022 (n8)

^[10] Ibid

^[11] Murray 2023 (n8) pp.12; Foerg 2022 (n8)

^[12] Ibid

^[13] Creative Commons, 'About CC licenses', available at: <https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/cclicenses/>, accessed 14 May 2024

^[14] IRCAM Forum, 'IRCAM License', available at <https://forum.ircam.fr/legal/contrat-de-licence-forum-ircam/> accessed 14 May 2024

^[15] Creative Commons, 'CC BY NC SA' available at: accessed 14 May 2024; Creative Commons, 'CC BY NC ND' available at: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/legalcode.en> accessed 14 May 2024

3.2 Legal and licensing framework for second use case phase

The NFT Token-Bound license is a recent very interesting development that could help address the legal challenges identified above. The NFT Token-Bound license consists in a copyright license specifically designed for NFTs by IC3 and COALA in 2023.^[1] The license follows a public conditional license model, borrowing some of the advantages of the CC model seen before, but introducing additional conditions that link the licence to the NFT.^[2] It applies to the public at large (hence “public”), but its enjoyment is conditional on ownership of the associated NFT to the licensed material (hence “conditional”).^[3] Only current token owners can therefore legally qualify as licensees thus the license virtually follows the token.^[4] As stated in the relevant terms of use, the licensor imposes no duty or obligation on the licensee, therefore no acceptance is required by the latter who receives it automatically when receiving the NFT.^[5] Such a framework purports to apply to any downstream sale of the NFT.^[6] When an NFT is transferred to a third person, the prior holder ceases being a licensee and the new holder receives a license under the exact terms as those of the prior licensee.^[7] The NFT Token-Bound license however does attempt to signal a licensor’s intent to be bound, clarifying the license becomes effective when invoked through a licensing process, understood broadly as any smart contract or technical process connecting an NFT with the license.^[8] The license is additionally compatible by design with the NFT licensing standard described in EIP 5218^[9], a smart contract interface supporting transfer, sublicensing, and revocation in copyright licensing.^[10] Any interface mirroring such functionalities will however be compatible.^[11]

In regards to license terms, the Token-Bound license provides a modular framework, once again partially inspired to the CC model, that allows users to customise the license by select and combine four independent licensing options^[12]:

Commercial v Non-commercial

Derivative v Derivative NFT v Derivative NFT Share-Alike v No derivative

Public license v No public license

Ledger authoritative v Legal authoritative

The license can firstly be either **Commercial** or **Non-commercial**, allowing or prohibiting commercial use of the linked work respectively. Users can furthermore select between different options to regulate the creation of derivative works. The **Derivative** option is the most permissive, allowing derivatives to be created in all circumstances. **No Derivatives** is the most restrictive, prohibiting derivatives entirely. **Derivative NFT** and **Derivative NFT Share-Alike** impose conditions on the creation of derivatives. The former requires the creation of an NFT on the same ledger and technical standard for the derivative work, while the latter requires the derivative be shared through the same licensing terms in addition to the creation of an NFT. The third license option **Public license** provides the choice to complement the conditional public license to token holders with a CC BY ND license. Per the license text this allows creators to grant the public at large use of the works but not to make derivatives, while reserving the right to create a derivative solely for NFT holders.^[13] The Token Bound license finally grants users the choice between a **Ledger authoritative** or **Legal authoritative** license. As specified in the license document, the **Ledger authoritative** option prescribes the blockchain ledger is authoritative in cases of any dispute over NFT ownership and entitlement to the license, while a **Legal authoritative** option clarify courts retain authority over such matters.^[14] The legal validity and enforcement of such conditions is however complex and remain to be assessed in D.6.1.

The NFT Token-Bound license model described could adequately address the main legal challenges identified in NFT licensing. By indirectly binding the NFT with the copyright license, the public conditional framework could arguably guarantee legal validity and enforcement in downstream sales. Unlike Creative

Commons, it furthermore allows for the retention of the main value proposition in the DAFNE+ business model, as the license can only be enjoyed by token holders rather than the public at large. While overcoming some of main challenge of applying CC licenses to NFTs, the Token-Bound license allows to retain the benefits of CC's public and standardised nature. It could reduce transaction costs and clarify licensing conditions in a reliable, easily communicable and digestible manner for users. Furthermore, the Token-Bound license's independent and modular framework may help provide a tailor-made approach that could suit the diverse needs of the DAFNE+ communities, ranging from the more dedicated to open culture to the more restrictive.

Due to the described characteristics, implementing the Token-Bound license in DAFNE+ could present a viable approach to ultimately transition from Creative Commons in the second Use-Case phase. The application of such a licensing framework to the DAFNE+ environment and Use-Cases however remains to be fully evaluated through in-depth legal analysis, provided in D6.1. Furthermore, the specific application of the license model and terms to the DAFNE+ environment is equally necessary to identify any challenges or opportunities that may arise and highlight areas for amendment. A legal assessment of the applicable platform liability regime, particularly under the DSA and E-commerce Directive framework, will also be relevant to the analysis of new NFT licensing frameworks. Given the inherently diverse nature of each use case, such legal analysis also requires an individualised assessment of the license application to each use case workflow. Topics to address include the possible presence of design rights alongside copyright in UC3, UC2's need to restrict access to works and select users allowed to create a derivative work, and the creation of private spaces/works in scenario 2.3.

^[1] IC3 and COALA, *The NFT Token-bound license* (2023)

^[2] Ibid 3-4

^[3] Ibid

^[4] Ibid

^[5] Ibid

^[6] ibid

^[7] Ibid

^[8] ibid

^[9] <https://eips.ethereum.org/EIPS/eip-5218>

[\[10\]](#) IC3 and COALA (n1) 3-4

[\[11\]](#) Ibid

[\[12\]](#) Ibid 4-7

[\[13\]](#) Ibid 7

[\[14\]](#) Ibid 2

4 Revenue model and monetisation framework

4.0 Introduction

During the first phase of the testing period, a series of workshops and webinars were performed with the users as per D5.1 “Use cases intermediary report”. The overall feedback we perceived is that users are interested and curious about the technology but find it complex and difficult to apply it in their context.

For this reason, we decided to implement the most basic structure both for the Governance and for the Compensation Mechanism. This will act as a base in order to start the conversation about definitions, functionalities and the identification of all modules and the interactions that take place, supporting us with the communication and the involvement of the community into the setting up of the most suited scenarios.

The monetisation framework plays an essential role as it is the main pillar into supporting users to gain parts of their livelihood from the platform, alimnts the platform funds, and so the common DAFNE+ Treasury and is therefore the motivation for users to join the platform.

In this initial use case period, the monetisation flow was analysed and defined to be implemented in a basic way, serving as a starting point for identifying and explaining the funding mechanism, the platform fees and the network transaction cost.

The current monetisation flow can be found in the D5.1 “Use cases intermediary report” section 3.3.1. It builds on the conclusions of D7.1 by maximising the income on NFTs by their owners and managing a redistribution fund to be allocated to community projects.

This structure should enable us to clearly calculate, explain and decide, together with the users, the best alternatives for moving forward. We keep in mind that community decisions on the monetisation system will remain biased as long as it remains in test-net with no actual financial transactions.

The next paragraphs list the possible scenarios of evolution of the model based on user feedback, and identifies the conditions needed in the pathway to mainnet.

4.1 Strategic factors for the model evolution

The basis of the model is to define the revenue stream from sales of assets.

It is built on top of a marketplace, whose purpose is to create a mechanism for many buyers and sellers to find each other.

The key concept of this strategy is to achieve the necessary traction, as it is based on high numbers of users and transactions.

Our aim is to increase the number of creators and art collectors on the platform as much as possible, in order to obtain a 'network effect'. That is why we will work on defining valid value propositions and incentives for both categories.

Our main challenge is to consolidate the communities for the three Use Cases, work with them on their sense of belonging and identification with these communities, to find together the right motivation to keep the community active in the participative governance.

In the next period, we will focus on identification of the following:

Key partners

- Anyone who already has the attention of the buyers and sellers we wish to attract

- Associations and Public administrations that want to support CCI
- Organisations that want to target or support creators

Key activities

- Attracting buyers
- Ensuring an adequate range of available assets
- Matching buyers & sellers
- Reputation system - think carefully about how to manage quality, as poor quality items or services will reflect badly on the marketplace.
- Clarify liability issues

Key resources

- Pool of willing buyers and sellers
- Test the mechanism that enables users to trade with each other, TRL of the platform and all the modules (preps for production state)

Value propositions

- Allow buyers to go to one place to access a range of products or skills to meet their needs
- Enable sellers to access buyers they would otherwise have difficulty reaching, or make the transactions easier in some way

Cost structure

- Infrastructure cost
 - Costs of moving to the Main-net (transaction fees)
 - Internal assessment of smart contracts (numbers and executions, cost)
 - External security and legal audit cost
- Advertising, marketing, and vetting costs

- Costs of subcontractors if you are managing the work
- Cost of any contract management activities you are performing, such as project management or quality control

Revenue streams

- Fee sharing model - Charge a transaction fee on completed deals
- Sell the products/services to the buyer, and subcontract
- Charge for access to the marketplace (e.g. a monthly fee to sellers that enables them to sell as much as they want)
- Charge for listing or advertising a particular want or need

Customer segments

- Research on the match between what the buyers want and what the sellers are offering

Customer relationships

- Facilitating different types of customer relationships including personal service, co-creation, and self-service

Channels

- Social media & local advertising
- Build relationships with sellers & repeat buyers
- Referrals and word of mouth

Revenue Stream - Membership sharing - Creating shared access to a community and/or other assets, as for example the tools catalogue

In the next period we will add documentation, guidelines and examples that can incentivise participation

4.2 Conditions for moving to mainnet

After having evaluated different test networks and requirements for moving to the mainnet we came to the conclusion that we will remain in testnet until the end of the project, preparing all the support, cost estimation and strategies for the production phase platform launch.

Nevertheless, this has an impact on motivating professional users in joining the development and testing period.

The main conditions we have identified therefore are:

- converting budget from the DAFNE+ platform to cryptocurrencies that can be used as prizes or incentives for motivating the onboarding of users and the assets exchange.
- defining the legal entity that will run the platform, either formed by users or by one of the consortium partners or another existing legal entity, in terms of legal responsibility, treasury management, platform maintenance and further development.
- carry out further technical developments of the platform up to TRL9 in order to reach the needed level of security for enabling financial transactions. This implies in particular supporting external security audit costs for smart contracts while still in development (with also new contracts to be added depending on the functional evolution of the platform features).
- supporting the mainnet transaction costs in the evolution of the business model.

The strategy for going into production will be described in detail in the D7.5 DAFNE+ exploitation report provided in the 36th month of the project.

5 DAO and governance

5.0 Introduction

DAOs are organisations that operate on the blockchain and are governed by rules encoded as smart contracts. These rules ensure that all members of the DAO have a fair and known representation and decision-making power. This ensures an equitable distribution of resources and the revenues generated by the platform.

The main goal of the DAO is to be collectively owned and governed by the users that can become owners and decision-makers of the platform and derive part of their livelihood from it.

The first elements of specification of the DAO were set out in D2.2, both from each use case and for the project as a whole, but as planned from the outset, the DAO operation is to start in the next use case period.

Its initial framework is presented hereinafter, along with the aspects that will be taken into account for its eventual evolution. It builds on feedback gathered by the use cases during their first phase, which overall showed participants' interest in getting involved in the governance of the platform via the DAO.

5.1 Initial governance and DAO framework

An analysis collecting the different voting systems, the token types and the implications for each, was performed and a first basic implementation was decided by the consortium for the first iteration. We defined the DAO proposals template, the voting mechanism and the initial technological stack.

FIGURE 1: DAFNE+ DAO STRUCTURE

5.1.0 Proposals

A DAO proposal is an idea that a member of the community wants the DAO to consider.

It describes the idea, how it will be implemented, and the funding requirements for executing the idea.

Proposal template:

- Title
- Budget
- Status: IDEA, DRAFT, V1
- Summary
- Timeline (for vote)
- Description
- Quorum (required for votes to be considered)

- Threshold (minimum number of votes a Proposal must obtain in order to be accepted)

We will start with 2 categories: Governance & Treasury

- Governance (DAO rules)
 - Fee value
 - Voting mechanism (+ Emergency)
 - Quorum & Thresholds values
- Treasury
 - New tech features – exp Propose to change the DAO model
 - New initiatives/ideas
 - Crisis Management - Super Admins

The users will have the possibility to initiate a proposal either using the Discord dedicated channels or directly in the DAFNE+ platform.

5.1.1 Voting system, direct voting

In this first implementation each registered user will be able to initiate a new proposal and vote on the existing ones. Each user will have one governance token that will be directly linked to the MetaMask wallet.

All the users will have the same voting power and delegation of the vote will not be allowed in this first phase. Each vote will be represented as a transaction on the blockchain, using the user's MetaMask public key for the cryptographic signature, ensuring authenticity and integrity. On-chain voting leverages the transparency and immutability of blockchain technology to provide a tamper-proof record of votes that can be audited by third parties.

Furthermore, we will set up a Super Admin role within the consortium members that will be able in this initial phase to:

- Define procedures for emergency situations that require immediate action, such as security breaches or protocol upgrades.
- Establish contingency plans and protocols for handling crises or unexpected events within the DAO.

The implementation is to be intended as a starting point supporting with clarifications and further analysis to be discussed, tested and validated with the users.

5.1.2 Communication channels

Discord is used as the main communication channel. In the last period, the conversion rate from events towards the Discord channels was below 1%.

For this reason, from the initial DAO specifications in D2.2, we opted for a simple architecture, dropping Discourse and focusing only on Discord for the time being.

We will add two new channels:

- o Governance - DAO rules: fee value, voting mechanism, Quorum & Thresholds values
- o Treasury: New tech features (exp Propose to change the DAO model), New initiatives/ideas

We will add guidelines for support, help-desk and bugs report.

5.2 Scenarios for possible evolutions

In the following period, we will concentrate on documenting each module of the system, build a context that can explain to non-tech users the implications of such a system, attract and involve the users in a participative development, explore together the next set-up and rules.

5.2.0 Token Management

- **Token Distribution:** Determine how tokens will be distributed among participants, founders, investors, and the community.
- **Token Utility:** Define the utility of the DAO's token within its ecosystem, such as voting rights, access to services, or revenue sharing.
- **Token Issuance:** Decide on the initial token supply and any mechanisms for token issuance or inflation. Create mechanisms for token issuance, such as minting new tokens, distributing tokens as rewards, or burning tokens.
- **Token Transfers:** Define rules for transferring tokens within the DAO, including any restrictions or conditions.
- **Token Staking and Locking:** Implement features for staking or locking tokens to participate in governance or access specific privileges
- **Token Voting:**
 - **Direct Voting:** Token holders directly vote on proposals according to their token holdings.
 - **Weighted Voting:** Give more weight to the votes of certain token holders, such as those who have staked more tokens or held them for longer periods.
 - **Quadratic Voting:** Allow token holders to express preferences using quadratic voting, which can help mitigate the influence of large stakeholders.
- **Liquid Democracy:**
 - **Delegated Voting:** Participants can delegate their voting power to representatives they trust, who then vote on their behalf.

- Vote Delegation: Allow participants to delegate their votes on specific issues or to specific individuals or groups.

5.2.1 Types and implications

- Dynamic NFTs
 - refers to NFTs that change over time – after they have been minted - based on external conditions or stimuli
- Utility NFTs
 - granting specific privileges to holders, such as access to specific communities, events, services or software
 - only certain users gain privileges and can vote
 - own governance tokens ERC-721
 - decide from the beginning how many we issue, the users can ‘buy’ voting power
- Non-transferable NFTs (or “soulbound”)
 - one wallet, one vote (users can create more wallets/accounts, Sybil attack)
 - membership cannot be sold

5.2.2 Governance Tokens

- Funds Allocation: Establish rules of reward mechanisms: reward participants for active engagement in governance activities, such as voting, proposing, or contributing to discussions.
- Governance Token Locking: Implement mechanisms to incentivise long-term participation and discourage short-term speculation, such as token locking or vesting schedules.
- Treasury Management: for allocating funds from the DAO’s treasury to support projects, initiatives, or operational expenses.
- Multi-Signature Wallets: implement multi-signature wallets or other security measures to control access to the DAO’s funds.

6 Monitoring and evaluation

6.0 Introduction

DAFNE+ platform's monitoring and evaluation task is based on different metrics (both quantitative and qualitative), initially introduced in D2.2 "DAFNE+ Use case specifications", section 6.3.

Those metrics are (reported from D2.2 hereunder to facilitate reading):

- **Platform and tool metrics:** Platform and tool metrics collected from web-based user interactions, using a combination of database data and web-analytics software (an instance of the open-source software [Matomo](#)).
 - **Social network analysis:** a subset of the platform and tools metrics, measure interactions and relationships between users. These interactions can help measure success factors for artists and creators, or how clusters and groups of users are created.
- **User surveys:** User surveys provide qualitative information about the user's perception of the platform and tools, often measured according to the Likert scale.
- **Expert surveys:** Expert's feedback to measure aspects such as the innovation of the project and other factors that regular users might not be able to answer. Also measured according to the Likert scale.
- **Demos:** Demos where users access the platform, use the tools of the project, and give their feedback. Usability and design insights can also be obtained from these experiments through observation of the users' behaviour with the tools.

6.1 Evolutions of the monitoring and evaluation framework

Given the list of metrics was rather extended, Task 5.4 started a series of consultations and workshops within the consortium, especially the use case partners, to refine and prioritise these metrics and the associated KPIs.

The following picture gives an impression of those workshops, namely a screenshot of a Miro board used as supporting material.

FIGURE 2: EXAMPLE OF MIRO BOARD FOR USE CASE KPI WORKSHOP

After the initial workshops several calls were held in order to finalise the results. This led to the following table for the KPIs (where KPIs are also given an ID to refer to them unequivocally):

KPI	Evaluation Means	Link to question (for surveys)
-----	------------------	--------------------------------

KPI_2 Integrity and transparency: 100% of information always available on the blockchain and attributable to the owner	Platform	
KPI_3 Privacy: GDPR fully compliant and 100% of instances of personal data correctly managed by the system.	Platform	
KPI_4 A modular platform that enables the creation of media content items, and their NFT-based distribution, sharing and governance.	Platform	
KPI_5 Reduction of time to create NFTs for creators and artists with respect to using separate and non-automated tools ≥ 4 (in 5 points Likert scale)	User Survey	QU_4a How easy was it to create an NFT for your asset? QU_4b If you have used other platforms where you create NFTs for your content, is it faster/easier to create NFTs with DAFNE+?
KPI_6 Usage of provided production components/workflows > 1 per creator	Platform	
KPI_7 Number of items shared by creators > 1 per creator	Platform	
KPI_32 Short term: Number of artwork production setups (work repositories) published > 5	Platform	
KPI_8 Number of re-use of community-shared items > 2 per creator	Platform	

KPI_9 Creators generating tokens daily >2%	Platform	
KPI_10 Users that perform any action on the platform weekly >15%	Platform	
KPI_11 Users that perform any action on the platform monthly >25%	Platform	
KPI_12 At least 200 participants in the pilots	Platform	
KPI_13 User satisfaction rate with the DAFNE+ platform ≥ 4 (in 5 points Likert scale)	User Survey	QU_1 Are you satisfied with the DAFNE+ platform?
KPI_15 Use Case 1: At least 100 registered users	Platform	
KPI_16 Use Case 2: At least 50 registered users	Platform	
KPI_17 Use Case 3: At least 50 registered users	Platform	
KPI_25 Short term: Easiness to use DAFNE+ content creation tools > 4 (in 5 points Likert scale)	User Survey	QU_2 Are DAFNE+ content creation tools easy to use?
KPI_26 Short term: Easiness to use DAFNE+ NFT application of content distribution > 4 (in 5 points Likert scale)	User Survey	QU_3 Is DAFNE+ NFT creation easy to use?
KPI_28 Short term: Satisfaction from the DAFNE+ distribution model in DAFNE+ sectors > 4 (5 points Likert scale)	User Survey	QU_5 Are you satisfied with the means the DAFNE+ provides you with to collaboratively own content?

KPI_29 Medium term: Satisfaction from the DAFNE+ distribution model in other sectors > 4 (5 points Likert scale)	Experts' survey	QE_6 Assuming that you consider that the revenue distribution models supported by DAFNE+ are appropriate for other sectors, how satisfying/appropriate do you consider them to be?
KPI_19 Short term: New workflows defined and enabled by DAFNE+ >3	Experts' survey	QE_1 During your experimentation, you followed a certain workflow. Would you propose a different or additional one that would better suit your needs or would meet the needs of a colleague of yours? Please, explain.
KPI_20 Short term: New business models defined and supported by DAFNE+ platform > 4	Project result	
KPI_1 Increase in possibilities for media creators and composers to control own communities without external interferences \geq 4 (in 5 points Likert scale)	User survey	QU_8 DAFNE+ aspires to increase your possibilities to control your own communities without external interferences. Do you agree with this statement?
KPI_18 Short term: Increase in innovation capabilities of the CCI workers involved in the project \geq 4 (in 5 points Likert scale)	Experts' survey	QE_12 Do you believe that DAFNE+ increases the innovation capabilities of CCI workers/creative creators?
KPI_21 Medium term: Decrease in time to market due to the exploitation of DAFNE+ tools >20%	Experts' survey	QE_2 DAFNE+ aspires to decrease the time to market due to the exploitation

(judged by external to the consortium people engaged in workshops)		of DAFNE+ tools. Estimate this decrease based on your experience.
KPI_27 Medium term: Intention to adopt DAFNE+ platform and/or tools within CCI > 4 (in 5 points Likert scale)	User Survey	QU_6 How likely is it that you continue to use the DAFNE+ platform and/or its tools?
KPI_14 At least 10 non cultural industries interested in the pilots' results.	Experts' survey	QE_3 Do you consider that NFT-based marketplaces would be of interest to other industries (beyond CCI)? QE_4 If you answered yes in the previous question, please name the relevant industries
KPI_22 Short term: Number of sectors for which DAFNE+ application has been investigated and evaluated with experts > 3	Project result	
KPI_23 Short term: Credibility of the study (assessed by external experts) > 8 (10 points scale)	Experts' survey	QE_7 You were presented with the study of DAFNE+ consortium on the replication of its approach to other sectors. How credible do you consider this study?
KPI_24 Medium Term: Increase in the innovation potential of additional sectors as estimated by external experts > 15%	Experts' survey	QE_5 The innovation potential of the above-named sectors would increase. How much?

KPI_31 Medium term: Increase of the level of EU media sector internationalisation due to DAFNE+ > 5%	Experts' survey	QE_8 Do you believe that DAFNE+ improves the potential for the internationalisation of the EU media sector? How much?
KPI_33 Long term: Increase of the level of engagement of citizens with the media industry >= 4 (in 5 points Likert scale)	Experts' survey	QE_9 Do you believe that DAFNE+ increases the level of citizens engagement with the media industry?
KPI_34 Long term: Increase in the user generated content market in EU due to DAFNE+ >= 4 (in 5 points Likert scale)	Experts' survey	QE_10 Do you believe that DAFNE+ increases the user generated content market in EU?
KPI_35 Long term: Increase of the number of European content creators in CCI >= 4 (in 5 points Likert scale)	Experts' survey	QE_11 Do you believe that DAFNE+ increases the number of European content creators in CCI?

TABLE 1: UPDATED LIST OF KPIS

Use cases partners had defined other metrics of particular interest for their use cases (as reported for example in D2.2). Given there was some redundancy across the different pilots, also these metrics were the object of an exercise in clarifying the meaning and eliminating duplicates. The result is in the following table:

Metric	Evaluation Means	Use case Partner
M_1 As a creative, are you able to sustain your livelihood through profits generated from open-source projects? If yes, can you explain how? If not, what challenges are you facing?	User Survey	IAAC

M_23 Average time to learn how to use the platform	Platform	IAAC
M_30 Abandonment rate: percentage of users who leave the funnel before completing a specific action	Platform	IAAC
M_31 Referral rate: percentage of users referred by DAFNE+ users	Platform	IAAC
M_32 Community Care Index: level of care and support experienced by users within the platform	User Survey	IAAC
M_9 Overall perception of empowerment among creators	User Survey	IRCAM
M_16 Average social media interactions per artwork and artist	Platform/Social Media	IRCAM
M_17 Average number of unique interactions per artwork	Platform	IRCAM
M_18 Average revenue per piece of art	Platform	IRCAM
M_25 Task completion rate of creating/purchasing a NFT	Platform	IRCAM
M_33 Average number of connections, interactions or collaborations established between users	Platform	IRCAM
M_6 Average amount of carbon dioxide equivalent emissions generated during the process of creating and distributing an NFT	User Survey	SODA
M_7 Average perceived transparency of the DAFNE+ platform	User Survey	SODA
M_28 Proportion of users who assess the usability of the DAFNE+ system as satisfactory based on their responses to the System Usability Scale (SUS) questionnaire	User Survey	SODA

M_29 Average amount of time it takes for creators to produce a single Non-Fungible Token (NFT) within the platform	Platform	SODA
M_38 Rate of artists stopping using the platform	Platform	SODA
M_39 Rate of artists with at least one sale out of the total number of artists who produced any NFTs	Platform	SODA
M_20 Cost-effectiveness of the solution in terms of the resources required to implement and maintain it	User Survey	SODA, UPM
M_3 Percentage of users that do not understand the rules of the DAFNE+ platform	User Survey	UPM
M_4 Percentage of revenue that goes to creators on the DAFNE+ platform	Platform	UPM
M_12 Percentage of users perceiving the platform as fair in revenue distribution.	User Survey	UPM
M_21 Number of transactions enabled by the platform	Platform	UPM
M_27 Likelihood of users to recommend the platform	User Survey	UPM
M_35 Number of NFTs purchased through the platform	Platform	UPM
M_36 Number of derivative works generated through the platform	Platform	UPM
M_37 Number of referrals	Platform	UPM
M_40 Total and Average number of pieces created by active users	Platform	ALL
M_41 Total and Average revenue of active users	Platform	ALL

M_42 Diversity of DAFNE+ platform's users	User Survey	ALL
M_43 Percentage of users perceiving the platform as fair in ecological impact.	User Survey	UPM

TABLE 2: USE CASE METRICS

For KPIs and metrics whose means of evaluation is “Platform”, we will often use a functionality of Matomo that consists in defining “goals” that are worth tracking. A goal is for example connecting a MetaMask wallet to the DAFNE+ platform, or tracking user paths through the pages of the platform’s website.

This mechanism can offer more details to track particular user actions of interest, with respect to the data that is logged by e.g. the platform server, and it is thus a preferred method.

We have for the moment defined the following goals:

- User registration (already tracked but not through Matomo)
- User links his/her wallet
- User uploads content (already tracked but not through Matomo)
- User offers content in marketplace (already tracked but not through Matomo)
- User sells content in the marketplace (already tracked but not through Matomo)
- User buys content in marketplace (already tracked but not through Matomo)
- User uses a tool from the tools’ catalogue (already tracked but not through Matomo)
- User uses the DAFNE+ communication channel
- User invites other people to join the platform (recommendation percentage)
- User downloads content

More goals will be defined to cover all the platform-evaluated KPIs and metrics presented in this section.

The necessary modifications to the platform to trigger the tracking of the above-mentioned initial goals are planned for M24.

7 Conditions for the sustainability of DAFNE+

To ensure the sustainability and growth of the DAFNE+ platform, integrating community-driven revenue models with decentralised, transparent governance is crucial. By leveraging non-fungible tokens (NFTs) and user-generated content, the platform can create a robust economic environment where creators are incentivised to contribute and monetise their work. This model not only fosters a self-sustaining revenue stream but also enhances user engagement and investment in the platform's future.

Simultaneously, the platform's governance should be managed through a decentralised autonomous organisation (DAO), where all major decisions are made collectively by the community. This transparency ensures that all stakeholders have a voice in the evolution of the platform, aligning with open-source principles that encourage collaboration, innovation, and trust. Such a governance model empowers users by giving them direct control over policy changes and resource allocation, further aligning their interests with the platform's success.

1. Revenue Diversification

- Follow the business model described in the project.
- Seek strategic partnerships with established tech companies for cross-promotion and shared revenue opportunities.

2. Community-Driven Revenue

- Encourage the community to create and sell their own content, providing them with a percentage of the sales.
- Explore the potential of DAO's vault/wallet initiatives for new features or community-driven projects.

3. Open-Source Development

- Foster a collaborative environment where developers can contribute to the platform's codebase.
- Set up a system for recognising and rewarding community contributions to encourage ongoing participation.
- Ensure that contributions are aligned with the platform's roadmap and quality standards.

4. Transparent Governance

- Utilise a Decentralised Autonomous Organisation (DAO) to give users a voice in the decision-making process.
- Establish clear guidelines for proposals and voting to ensure a fair and transparent governance structure.
- Regularly publish reports on governance activities to maintain transparency and accountability.

5. Legal Entity

- The possibility of continued platform operation after the end of the DAFNE+ project requires the establishment of a legal entity that would take over the platform management. The necessary conditions include the existence of a network of stakeholders interested in collaborating towards these objectives and agreements by project partners to give access to elements of intellectual property they developed in the project.
- Additionally, this legal entity must comply with Web3 rules and regulations. This includes, but is not limited to, the implementation and maintenance of a cryptowallet to facilitate secure and transparent transactions on the platform. This cryptowallet will be used for various purposes, such as processing payments, managing digital assets, and ensuring the integrity of transactions within the platform ecosystem. Specifically, the wallet will be utilised to gather fees and maintain the costs associated with operating the platform, ensuring its sustainability and continued service.

6. Expertise Sharing

- Support the creative industry and their communities in developing knowledge and skills on shared ownership and platform cooperativism. Organising events and activities where the focus is on the experience, and learning happens
- Support new ideas and initiatives coming from the bottom-up approach
- Share the experience and the outcomes in open formats – toolkits, documentation and guidelines that can be used for further research and practice

By implementing these strategies, DAFNE+ aims to build a robust and dynamic ecosystem that not only sustains itself financially but also fosters innovation and community engagement, ensuring its longevity and relevance in the ever-evolving digital landscape.

8 Use case 1 - User generated content at large for heritage

8.0.0 Introduction

DAFNE+ aims to support a diverse group of professionals including prosumers, content creators, journalists, and creatives. These individuals are engaged in producing a wide range of content using visual, sound, and artistic media. The primary focus of DAFNE+ in Use case 1 is to encourage the creation and dissemination of content that promotes and preserves cultural heritage. This involves not only documenting and sharing historical and cultural information but also presenting it in innovative and engaging way that can reach and impact a broad audience. Whether through digital storytelling, multimedia projects, or artistic expressions, the goal is to keep cultural heritage alive and relevant to their communities.

Primary users of DAFNE+ in Use Case 1.2 are students at Manchester Metropolitan University's School of Digital Arts involved in the many collaborative units that emphasise the importance of collaboration and experimentation in the digital and creative sector. They compose work with a wide range of media: video (film and animation), 3D games engine-based media, sound and music, XR and other interactive experiences on a range of topics including local heritage. Students need to be able to create work as part of a group working on a project, without diluting or confusing their claim to specific aspects of creative development. In addition, students would also be able to share more widely their work as an asset in the 'Shareloom'. Shareloom is the proposed DAO for Use Case 1 which has been set up to facilitate a creative community that includes students and partner organisations, which shares and exchanges creative assets.

From the feedback from the Creative Jam, which was run at SODA in January 2024, we gained valuable insight and feedback with regards to students, staff and industry partner's attitudes towards the DAFNE+ platform. Much of the feedback oscillated around collaboration, ownership and smart contracts. The platform was considered innovative and to be promoting a fair and socially just framework for collaboration across digital art forms. Users were interested in an increased understanding of the complex world of smart contracts and would have appreciated models, or more 'landscaping' in terms of the legal and ethical considerations at play when engaging in smart contracts. Students were still interested in NFTs but more for ways in which they

could be used to drive different futures for digital content other than for simple economic remuneration. Comprehending the needs and attitudes of our Use Case community is essential for the design of the DAFNE+ platform as it helps inform the technical partners about the needs of those who are just setting out on their career journeys and pathways.

The DAFNE+ platform was considered a useful tool by members of the Use Case 1 ecology. There was general agreement that there needed to be clearer explanations and examples of platform functionality and wider legal/economic ramifications having engaged with the technology.

8.1 Scenario 1.1: Prosumers in the Cultural Heritage

8.1.0 User profiles

The user profile of this case scenario is a diverse group of professionals including prosumers, content creators, journalists, and creatives. These individuals are engaged in producing a wide range of content using visual, sound, and artistic media. We can differentiate two roles:

- Creator/Author: creates artistic assets individually
- Collaborator: participates in the creation of a collaborative piece of artwork

8.1.1 Managed assets

Most of the assets used by our users would be audio, video and image files due to their ability to create all types of content: visual, sound, and artistic. Each piece of content will be considered and art piece or artwork

8.1.2 Promotional materials

- Title.
- Author/s.
- Description.
- Media Type / Multiple Media Type.
- Snapshot.
- Traits, metadata of the characteristics and its rarity.

- If is part of a collection the link to the whole collection.

8.1.3 Conditions for implementation

As this technology is fairly new and not well known by the general public, we will need a lot of educational support on how to use this technology.

- Technology (blockchain, wallet, network usage)
- Engagement with the community: on values and trust

8.1.4 User journeys

As for the content creator user persona the journey would be as follows:

1. A brief presentation about how DAFNE+ platform works, supported by tutorial videos on how to sign up to the platform and how to create a wallet (if needed).
2. Sign up to DAFNE+ platform and create an account.
3. Show with tutorials support on how to create content, how the marketplace works, and how to use the tools gathered in the platform.
4. Ready to address some common matters:
 - a. Security of their artwork (theft)
 - b. Licenses (first and second market)
 - c. DAO

8.2 Scenario 1.2: Students from MMU School of Digital Arts

8.2.0 Scenario description

In previous document D2.2 the user profile for our case study is the SODA creative media student working as part of team who must produce artwork using [North West Film Archive](#) (NWFA)* and/or other footage from MMU's NFT Shareloom student and staff, for community arts events organised as part of DAFNE+ testing – a gallery exhibition.

8.2.1 User profile

The profile was updated for the Creative Jam activities, reflecting its format (international collaborative teaching and learning scenario) and themes (fairer futures, the disruptive prospect of creative AI technologies

and other future facing concerns). In this setting, the NWFA and Shareloom elements were not required. However, the overall profile of the student based on user feedback from MMU remained with some minor amendments to make the persona more relevant to a wider section of the participants.

User profiles:

- **SODA media student user persona**
- Lecturers (such as members of the MMU project team)
- external content providers, external audience and commissioners

SODA media student user persona:

20-year-old Level 5 SODA (currently) undergraduate student who uses tools including: Photoshop, After Effects, Premiere, Unreal Engine, Logic and Blender. Use AI automation tools to do initial designs and mockups for work. Share content almost exclusively on social media channels: Instagram, Tik Tok, Vimeo, Youtube, Discord and Reddit. They have some knowledge of blockchain and NFT technologies but do not currently own a crypto wallet. Most of the work they currently produce is for educational outputs. However, when they consider selling their work online through DAFNE+, the top three things they are concerned about are:

- protection from theft.
- ability to choose a suitable copyright agreement.
- fair and transparent pricing and payment.

Students in the school are involved in the many collaborative units that emphasise the importance of collaboration and experimentation in the digital and creative sector. A key use case scenario will be the preparation of creative work for student shows or cohort presentations.

Secondary users testing:

Lecturers (such as members of the MMU project team) responsible for facilitating interactions with DAFNE+ and moderating Shareloom student event communications and delivery mechanisms, creating educational

projects and public events that build a DAFNE+ DAO project community and forum based on SODA students, their networks, and audiences.

Other users not tested include external content providers, external audience and commissioners.

8.2.2 Managed assets

1. a single asset, e.g., a film or 3D asset like an environment based on historical footage.
2. a configuration of assets, e.g., a film, a 3D asset, a projection mapping sequence and a performance script
3. documentation of a project, e.g., a video of the installation being developed and its final outcome.

8.2.3 Promotional materials

- MMU marketing dept “Future Me” events promotional web material
- MMU SODA social media announcements and news
- MMU lecturer in-class and VLE platform Moodle announcements and endorsements
- DAFNE+ advert and slides presented and shared as part of academic events including Storytellers + Machines creative AI conference

8.2.4 Conditions for implementation

- Non-commercial/educational tier
- Accessible and moderated communities space
- Easy to collaborate and share credit/income
- Full GDPR compliancy
- Positive and transparent environmental and social values

8.2.5 User journeys

Based on user journey descriptions in D2.2, MMU identified core objectives to test from its wider use case in phase 1. Following Phase 1 testing, the SODA creative media student user journey is as follows:

8.2.5.1 SODA creative media student

Students are taking part in a teaching module (core teaching or for additional credits):

1. The student signs up to DAFNE+ platform using instructions given by their lecturer or an online teaching resource. At this point, they are not much invested in DAFNE+ platform and do not entirely understand what they will get out of it.
2. They follow instructions to set up a crypto wallet and can associate it with their account.
3. As part of their assignment, they must work on a project exploring fairer futures and the role of AI and NFT technology in that future (or a similar collaborative educational theme).
4. They discuss their ideas and communicate with lecturers on the Shareloom discord channel using supplementary presentation platforms such as Miro or Google Docs for creative documentation and creative tools for media production (e.g. Adobe Creative Suite)
5. They use the content in a collaborative project with others in their transdisciplinary group and once it is complete, they are able to mint an NFT with attribution made clear through the fractionalised credit. This might be:
 - a. a single stand-alone asset, e.g., a film or 3D asset like an environment based on historical footage.
 - b. A single asset for the purposes of a larger creative project (e.g. collaborative world building, music album)
 - c. a configuration of assets, e.g., a film, a 3D asset, a projection mapping sequence and a performance script
 - d. documentation of a project, e.g., a video of the installation being developed and its final outcome.
6. They present documentation of the work to other students as part of a virtual studio tour and for critique by peers and staff.
7. If go on to present their work in a show they are able to share a link via QR code or other easy link sharing method which takes the audience member to DAFNE+ to view and potentially purchase the work.

8.2.5.2 Secondary user journey: Staff

1. Staff sign up with the DAFNE+ platform and (if necessary, a wallet and test currency) use it to browse existing content and make lists of recommended assets for use in an upcoming project.
2. These assets are included as links in a learning resource or assignment brief.
3. Students share resultant work using the assets via DAFNE+ and Sharepoint channels.

8.3 Implementation strategy

8.3.0 Early adopters

- Teaching staff

The majority of the interaction with DAFNE+ in UC 1.2 will be facilitated by teaching and research staff in SODA. These staff represent expertise in core subject areas to our test population and have access to a large body of potential student participants from various levels of HEI degrees, from first-year undergraduate degrees to postgraduate masters.

- Student ambassadors from Phase 1 testing

Students from the Phase 1 testing have indicated that they would be interested in being part of future events, in which they would provide some level of context and explanation through sharing the work they produced in Creative Jam 1

- External champions and advisors

Final discussions are taking place with 2-3 external champions for the project from organisations such as broadcaster BBC and Web3 industry publication Right Click Save. However at least two have agreed in principle to take on this role. We expect this support to come in the form of paid lectures (as part of teaching activity) and media outputs related to the project and its aims.

8.3.1 Promotion

8.3.1.1 Panel on Web3 and AI at Storytellers+Machines conference

- School of Digital Arts, MMU, Manchester
- 2-4 July 2024

Storytellers + Machines 2024 is a transdisciplinary creative AI conference that champions the contributions of artists, creative practitioners and technologists, alongside other voices from academia, industry and cultural sectors in the lively and contested space. A panel presenting on Web3 and AI will feature Andrew King from the MMU team, Alex Estorick, a potential champion of the project in phase 2 as well as voices from industry and the cultural sector. The panel will be an opportunity to introduce staff and members of the wider SODA network to DAFNE+ and its offer to creative communities.

8.3.1.2 DAFNE+ Blockchain and NFT Partner Symposium

- Hybrid format (Manchester/Barcelona)
- Second week of July 2024

SODA in collaboration with FabLab Barcelona I IAAC are planning to deliver a DAFNE+ Blockchain and NFT Partner Symposium mid to late June 2024, a series of events that explore the transformative impact of NFTs across domains such as art, gaming, and fashion. These events aim to facilitate discussions on legal and regulatory considerations, environmental impacts, and the future directions of NFTs and provide a platform to share insights, spark discussions, and explore the vast potential of NFT and blockchain technologies.

Bringing together consortium members, our first event will serve as a forum for interdisciplinary dialogue, fostering collaboration and advancing scholarly understanding of the complex dynamics of NFTs and blockchain. Concluding with a forum exploring DAO mechanisms and opportunities for implementation of DAOs in future projects. It is also an opportunity for us to gather feedback about formats for future events taking place between October and December 2024.

We will be inviting submissions for short format presentations exploring the diverse range of blockchain research and development that the DAFNE+ partners have been working on within and outside of the DAFNE+ project.

8.3.1.3 DAFNE+ International Meet-up series (MMU + IAAC)

- Date: Between October - December 2024

A three-part meetup series focusing on gamification, phygital NFTs, and tokenomics. These short series events aim to acquaint participants with the DAFNE+ project and platform, fostering engagement and curiosity with diverse topics relevant to the creative community.

Attendees will also gain a preliminary knowledge for the forthcoming Creative Jam in January 2025, laying the groundwork for deeper exploration during the international seminar.

8.3.1.4 World Building Workshop series

October 2024 - January 2025 (TBD)

We are also planning a World Building Workshop series that will apply DAO-like mechanisms to collaborative world building scenarios and collecting feedback via DAFNE+ platform and other methods.

8.3.1.5 Creative Jam 2025

The second edition of the Creative Jam, in collaboration with IAAC, will take place in January 2025. The methodology, strategy, and experts involved will directly result from the previous engagements' feedback during the Creative Jam (Jan 2024) and the following activities developed from both Use Cases. This international hybrid event will involve students from across SODA and MMU and will feature alumni and Undergraduate students from the previous year, who will take on various roles in tutoring and supporting different aspects with their peers of testing the platform and leading to the 2025 event.

8.3.2 User support and community management

Students and their collaborators using the DAFNE+ platform will be supported by a SODA creative NFT focused initiative called Shareloom. Shareloom is a network created at SODA on [Discord](#) with the following values.

- Creating value and opportunities for students across MMU.
- Building a legacy of student work and community engagement.
- Working with sustainable blockchains.
- Experimenting with future facing technology to create exciting ‘phygital’ experiences.
- Maintaining an open, inclusive, and safe environment in our wider community.

Through Shareloom, we believe in the power of community-fostering activities as an essential driver to the future success of our students. Throughout DAFNE+ we have utilised Shareloom as a platform for workshops and exhibitions around NFT's, DAO's and the blockchain. We envisage a potential future for Shareloom to expand into a wider community as a formalised part of the DAFNE+ project.

8.3.3 Evaluation

Following the baseline feedback provided by the participants in the Creative Jam 1 event, UC1.2 will continue to monitor both the growth of the community and qualitative feedback related to platform use and possible future creative business models. We will gather this information iteratively to inform ongoing activities, such as the DAFNE+ meet-up series and world-building workshops taking place across the period of research. This approach will ensure that activities are responsive to the community and reflect emerging research interests and outputs.

9 Use case 2 - Experimental sound/music production

9.0 Introduction

The DAFNE+ Use case 2 - Experimental sound/music production builds on and extends IRCAM's corporate framework of articulation of technological research and contemporary artistic production. The addressed community includes on one side researchers, engineers, and companies involved in the production of creative technology, and on the other side artists and creatives using this technology including composers, performers, sound designers, and computer music designers. The use case also brings another category of users not part of IRCAM's community: NFT collectors and art sponsors. The focus is on live interactive computer music, but with more and more extensions to the use of advanced sound and music technologies in other creative areas including performing arts, installations, sound design, etc. Therefore, the use case title was extended to explicitly including this sound creative dimension present in other activity sectors than music. A specificity of the use case in the emerging landscape of blockchain/NFT based platforms for sound and music, related to the "experimental" attribute, is that the assets to be managed are not only fixed media such as sound files of music or sound recordings, but pieces of code and related data necessary for the (re)production of sound/music artworks, especially when they are interactive, and also more complex fixed media audio/music formats currently not supported in other blockchain platforms, such as for multichannel audio.

The use case is structured in 3 scenarios based on the assets to be managed:

1. Creation and use of components
2. Creation and use of work repositories
3. Creation and use of works / private spaces

9.1 Scenario 2.1 – Creation and use of components

9.1.0 Scenario description

This scenario concerns the distribution and use of software components for audio/music creative processes (libraries, applications, datasets, etc.). Novel possibilities enabled by the blockchain include its use for declaring software anteriority, NFTs supporting crowd-funded code development in the spirit of Patreon, and its complementarity to open-source software distribution for protecting non-public domain components, such as datasets resulting from artistic processes (performance recordings) that can be stored in the platform and made available conditionally to the acquisition of an NFT associated to a license in the form of a smart contract.

Components authors (developers of creative functions and tools) store their assets on existing platforms like github, gitlab or IRCAM Forum for archiving, sustainability, publication, self-promotion or sale. They also see it as a practical way to make assets available for collective activities such as co-creation, workshop support or academic publication. These platforms have recently integrated mechanisms for sponsorship between their members ([github](#) since June 2022 for instance). More and more independent developers are using sites like [Patreon](#) to distribute their releases only to people who have subscribed to a paid membership. Finally, some authors of creative libraries do not hesitate to create their own [e-commerce site](#) to sell applications and services. Sharing data and learning scripts for machine learning is becoming increasingly popular, with sites like [kaggle](#).

The approach for this scenario is to build on IRCAM's Forum, define ways of interfacing both frameworks by handling related technical and legal issues, and focus on the development of new features that emerge as potentially interesting advances for users:

- Development of new advanced tools for sound/music processing and synthesis.
- Use of the blockchain as a reference for formalising authorship (individual or collective) on creative software production as an alternative to software deposit.
- Enhanced management of component versioning and publication.
- Better support of collective work, be it on development including beta-testing, or in groupware for artistic production and/or education using components.

- Experimentation of new monetisation schemes for creative software distribution.
- Sharing audio data and pre-trained AI-RAVE models.

9.1.1 User profiles

- Component Author: developer, researcher, company.
- Component Collaborator: collaborator in the development/maintenance of a component: creative in the loop, student, etc.
- Component User: creative – composer, computer music designer, sound engineer, performer...

9.1.2 Managed assets: Components

A component is a technical element whose integration gives access to generic functionalities. It is a high-level entity (package, library, compressed folder), grouping multiple files of heterogeneous data types: Standalone, application, software, libraries, program, script and patches: max library, max package, maxforlive device, puredata external, python, colab, AI model, 3D model, Sound bank, Dataset...

This element can be hosted by the platform under DAFNE+ license or can be referenced by the platform with delegation of license to a third party – Github, IRCAM Forum, bitbucket, third party websites. Example components provided as part of WP3 are:

- [Dicy2](#) library: Max Package for music generativity and improvisation.
- [CoMo](#) and [SoundWorks](#) libraries: javascript and apps for collective interaction with distributed audio/music devices.
- [Spat](#) library: Max Package for sound spatialisation.
- [RAVE, RAVE2 and nn-](#): Python script, AI-RAVE models and Max Package for deep learning for sound synthesis/processing.

9.1.3 Promotional materials

- Description of the asset using modern WYSIWYG interface including
 - Asset description: Free description of the asset with video, picture and sound integration.
 - Asset version: date of publication, version number, release notes.
 - Uploaded illustrations, jpg, gif, video...

- Links to additional contents: Documentation, tutorials, website...
 - Public access to these promotional materials without requiring prior user registration to the platform.
- Used license(s), and monetisation conditions
- Dependencies
 - List of contributors: author, collaborators, referencer...
 - Dependency tree of DAFNE+ internal and external assets.
 - Related asset (most proximate assets according to AI search engine).
 - Membership of an institution or collective
- DAFNE+ platform context
 - DAO/Community/tribe.
 - Categories.
 - Tags.
 - Related data from Internal reputation system

9.1.4 Conditions for implementation

- Technically and easily accessible
- Low financial entry-level barrier
- Easy user engagement: interface, experience
- Transparency: Explicit social and environmental values (with an understanding of what fair and sustainable means)
- Trust
- Sustainability after the project's conclusion
- Clarity of licensing conditions and compatibility with licenses under which components are already published. In particular, the compatibility with the IRCAM Forum license (for components already published on it) requires non-commercial use and, for most items, preventing re-distribution outside of the platform.

- Depending on situations, real financial benefits from selling on a production market. This condition requires real financial transactions through mainnet.

9.1.5 User journeys

- **Component Author journey:** The Component Author uploads a new component, may declare shared ownership on given proportions with other users, declares publication options (public/reserved to DAFNE+ platform users/conditional to NFT ownership, etc.), completes the necessary metadata, promotional materials and a sales price.
- **Component Collaborator journey:** A Component collaborator can ask for access to the component. Once the Component Producer accepts, the Component collaborator can access the back office of the component, download it and upload a new version of it. The Component Producer can define the amount of co-authorship for each of the collaborators.
- **Component User journey:** After explicitly accepting the necessary conditions, Component User can download a component and use it to create a repository, an artwork, or another component for his/her own use.

9.2 Scenario 2.2 – Creation and use of work repositories

9.2.0 Scenario description

Artists, creatives, archivists, musicologists, music/sound producers need a shared database of the technical elements that intervene in the production or reproduction of artworks. A frequent setup for mixed music works combining instruments on stage and computer-generated sounds or processes concerns the programs, the related data and the technical configuration needed to execute the piece during the performance.

This scenario aims to support the technical and legal foundations of an open database of sound/music work repositories: in the international computer music community, and despite various expressed marks of interest and local approaches there has been up to now no large-scale infrastructure developed for that purpose. The

setting of such an open work repertoire gathers converging interests of composers, computer music designers, performers, performance venues and musicologists, and even possibly collectors who would like to acquire rights on the technical form of major works that are expected to be milestones in the history of sound and music aesthetics.

The initial focus was on computer music, but positive feedback from artists and sound designers has led us to extend the scope to the latter: in commercial sound design or urban installations, declaring the work in the blockchain before submitting it for tender can provide a kind of security against copying. The possible formats are very open and can include the algorithms used to compose the piece, the patches to perform it, but also multichannel recordings, that are currently not supported by most NFT marketplaces. A major problem identified in many cases is that work repositories can include copyrighted content, such as scores or recordings.

The general approach is to store such content privately, and only allow access to it subject to the acquisition of an NFT associated with a smart contract license that will specify the conditions of use acceptable to the repository right holders, including third parties not part of the DAFNE+ community. If these conditions are not met, restrictions may apply to repositories to be published on the DAFNE+ platform, restricting them to repositories that do not contain copyrighted material belonging to third parties, thus limiting DAFNE+'s representativeness of the repertoire of existing pieces. In addition, the platform specification provides for the management of versions of work repositories, i.e. several blockchain work repository assets linked to the same work of art, with the choice given to the original owner either to authorise anyone to produce a new version, or to prevent it by default and be able to select the users of his/her choice who will be trusted to respect the original artistic intent and make relevant choices accordingly.

9.2.1 User profiles

- Repository Author: Mainly artists – composers, computer music designers, sound designers
- Repository Collaborator: Collaborator in the development/maintenance of a Repository. Same profiles.
- Repository User:

- Composer, computer music designer, sound engineer, sound designer
- Music performers (individuals, ensembles, orchestras), performing artists, music and art venues, score publishers, sponsors.
- Musicologist and archivist

9.2.2 Managed assets: work repositories

A technical element whose implementation allows the production or reproduction of a specific work. A repository is a high-level entity, grouping multiple files of heterogeneous data types: A zip, a dmg file or a folder that contains the code, programs, data, library dependencies, documentation (including published score), and any other references or metadata to implement a creative process. The repositories usually contain, together with all needed programs and data, the following documentation:

- Differences with previous versions if any.
- Installation instructions.
- Tech rider and hard/soft-ware combination.
- System calibration and tests.
- Initialisation routine.
- Technical instructions.
- Performance notes/score.
- Audio recording excerpts (optional)
- Notes for the people who will open this documentation in a late future.

9.2.3 Promotional materials

- Description of the asset using modern WYSIWYG interface including
 - Asset description: Free description of the asset with video, picture and sound integration.
 - Asset version: date of publication, version number, release notes.
 - Uploaded illustrations, jpg, gif, video...
 - Basic work presentation, including link to work documentation such as in the IRCAM [Brahms](#) contemporary music works database.
 - Links to additional contents: Documentation, tutorials, website...

- Public access to these promotional materials without requiring prior user registration to the platform
- Use license(s) and monetisation conditions
- Dependencies
 - List of contributors: author, collaborators, referencer...
 - Dependency tree of DAFNE+ internal and external assets.
 - Related asset (most proximate assets according to AI search engine).
 - Membership of an institution or collective
- DAFNE+ platform context
 - DAO/Community/tribe.
 - Categories.
 - Tags.
 - Related data from Internal reputation system

9.2.4 Conditions for implementation

- Technically and easily accessible
- Low financial entry-level barrier
- Easy user engagement: interface, experience
- Transparency: Explicit social and environmental values (with an understanding of what fair and sustainable means)
- Trust
- Sustainability after the project's conclusion
- Licensing conditions:
 - For work repositories containing copyrighted materials owned by third parties other than the asset owners and/or subject to restricted distribution by their owners: an acceptable framework for these stakeholders would be to grant a right of personal use conditional to the acquisition of an NFT. This license must prevent re-distribution (including commercial use) and must be limited in time to the period of experimentation of the DAFNE+ project.

- For the production of derivatives including new versions of work repositories: 2 options were identified depending on situations : i) either anyone is allowed to produce a new version, or ii) the owners of the initial version shall be able to decide to select users that will be allowed to produce a new version while respecting the artistic intentions of the work's author. In both cases, new versions must be distributed under the same conditions as previous versions (share alike).

9.2.5 User journeys

9.2.5.1 Publication of a Repository

The Repository Author:

1. Creates a work repository
2. uploads a local package
3. defines ownership of the Repository version
 - Split of Repository version IP between various contributors (as registered users).
 - Possibility of allowing a percentage of ownership (credit) to existing components/repositories.
 - After the sale of the corresponding NFT, the contributors get the same money as a percentage of the total value.
4. defines publication options:
 - public/reserved to DAFNE+ registered users/conditional to NFT ownership
 - NFT value
 - forking options
 - user-license
5. defines version of the repository
6. describes the repository with promotional material in the CMS with audio/video player, web interface to work performance, etc.
7. describes the repository with used components and every dependency of the application of the repository code

8. [Possible step] Assessment of the quality of the repository by peer-review / moderation by a moderator
9. uploads new versions in the CMS with content versioning management.

After the publication, the platform automatically announces the creation of a new repository for advertisement - featured in catalogues, Discord & social networks.

9.2.5.2 Publication of a new version of the Repository / Maintenance of a Repository:

If the Repository is published under a license enabling derivatives, the Repository collaborators get access to it through the marketplace.

In the other case, the Repository collaborator requests access to the Repository Producer according to DAO rules and publication options. The Repository Producer (owner) accepts or denies the request (the decision implies all stakeholders if numerous).

Ownership rights on the new work Repository version are shared between the Repository collaborator and owners of previous versions of the work Repository versions including the initial owners (of first declared version) following a redistribution mechanism defined in the DAO rules.

Repository Referencer journey: the Repository Referencer can create a Repository by referencing an existing one, possibly hosted by another platform. She links the download button to an existing URL and the description to an already existing content.

9.2.5.3 Use of a Repository

The Repository User:

1. buys an NFT
2. obtains the rights to use the repository according to publication options and DAO's rules.
3. downloads a zip file
4. can fork the repository as a new repository if allowed.

9.3 Scenario 2.3 – Creation and use of works / private spaces

9.3.0 Scenario description

The idea is to transpose crowdfunding processes to experimental sound/music creation using NFTs: fans and collectors will be invited to contribute to the funding of an ongoing creation process against counterparts (“private spaces”) to be defined by the artists and their commissioners in smart contracts, including VIP access to the work premiere, invitation to follow the production process, exchange sessions with the artists, mention of their names as part work sponsors, etc.

9.3.1 User profiles

A work author or producer creates a private space and invites people to join it according to the conditions defined in the DAO. A user of the private space who has bought an NFT can enter the private space and access exclusive content.

9.3.1.1 Creator/manager of a private space

An artist or creative and or his/her producer who wants to exchange exclusive content with her/his fan base/sponsors.

9.3.1.2 Work user: Buyer of a Work / Subscriber to a private space

- General public
- Art sponsor, NFT collector
- Cultural institution, performance venue

9.3.2 Managed assets

Here the qualification as an asset is questionable. In this use case, the attribution of an NFT can concern either on a persistent resource in the blockchain such as a work or an ephemeral advantage such as an event ticket related to the work. Moreover, an important objective being to propose new ways of sponsoring a work in progress during its conception and production process, like crowdfunding, the scenario should enable to define a counterpart related to a notion of work project, not only to an already completed work.

In all cases, the counterpart to the NFT will be defined by the private space owner and directly managed by him/her with his/her subscribers.

For instance, for various forms of subscription to a work such as:

- Exclusive ownership of the work (unique sponsor).
- Shared ownership of the work, ownership of a limited edition of the work (multiple sponsors).
- Exclusive ownership of a unique variant of the work (parametrised work).

Counterparts may include:

- VIP access to work performance premiere.
- Access to the artist (private session).
- Personal dedication published with the work premiere documentation.
- Public sponsoring exposure.
- Use license (possibly time limited) of work repository for work performance.
- Tickets for performance/concert.
- Access to the artwork's "internals", i.e. underlying production algorithms.
- Behind the scene, exclusive stories and content.

9.3.3 Promotional materials

- Description of the asset using modern WYSIWYG interface including:
 - Asset description: Free description of the asset with video, picture and sound integration.
 - Asset version: date of publication, version number, release notes.
 - Uploaded illustrations, jpg, gif, video...
 - Basic work presentation, including link to work documentation such as in the IRCAM [Brahms](#) contemporary music works database.
 - Links to additional contents: Documentation, tutorials, website...
 - Visibility of the asset not subscribed to when joining the platform (The marketplace must be visible to those who do not have an account on the platform)
- Use license(s), monetisation conditions
- Dependencies
 - List of contributors: author, collaborators, referencer...

- Dependency tree of DAFNE+ internal and external assets.
 - Related asset (most proximate assets according to AI search engine).
 - Membership of an institution or collective
- DAFNE+ platform context
 - DAO/Community/tribe.
 - Categories.
 - Tags.
 - Related data from Internal reputation system

9.3.4 Conditions for implementation

- Technically and easily accessible
- Low financial entry-level barrier
- Easy user engagement: interface, experience
- Transparency: Explicit social and environmental values (with an understanding of what fair and sustainable means)
- Trust
- Sustainability after the project's conclusion
- Clarity and cross-compatibility of licensing scheme
- Real financial benefits from selling on a production market (mainnet...). This scenario is not realistic in the unique context of a test network (Amoy testnet...).

9.3.5 User journeys

9.3.5.1 Creation of a Work private space

A Private space Creator:

- Creates a private space.
 - References a work.
 - Specifies the private space content.
 - Defines NFT price following the DAO rules.
 - Invites Work collaborators and Work Users to share/visit the private space.

9.3.5.2 Use of a Work/Work project private space

A Work user:

- Can buy an NFT to access a private space.
- Benefits from the private space advantages.

9.4 Implementation strategy

Our overall strategy is to continue promoting the platform, mainly through scenarios 2.1 and 2.2 (scenario 2.3 will remain suspended until real financial transactions are possible). It is guided by the analysis of user feedback gathered in the previous phase (see D5.1). It is also being refined, since in addition to the management of work repositories, a complementary practice is emerging in the management of artistic resources (recordings, pre-trained AI models, datasets...).

Analysis of user feedback (see D5.1) shows that users are interested in using the platform to share not only finished works, but also artistic resources. They are motivated by various factors, including protection of their resources, access to other people's resources and collaboration with other creators. The survey suggests that the platform needs to improve its support for collaboration. Users want to be able to manage different versions of their resources. Creative Commons licenses are a popular option, but some users are interested in conditional access based on NFT. Although most users were not familiar with NFT, they appreciated the platform's ease of use. It is expected that the main network will be used for real financial transactions. The process of creating an account and using the platform was found to be complex. Users are generally satisfied with the platform but would like better communication and training on blockchain and NFTs. This community wants to use the platform for monetisation, distribution, collaboration and preservation of creative work and artistic resources.

One of the platform's most popular use case 2 tools is the new RAVE 2 tool. Its popularity, measured at the "RAVE party" organised as part of the IRCAM 2024 Forum workshops (see D5.1), could encourage increased use of the platform. Indeed, the tool is based on the exploitation and production of artificial intelligence

models learned from sound data. The learning phases of these models consume a lot of GPU computing time, and therefore energy. Sharing these models, once trained, is an ecological challenge in the computing space. We would therefore like to offer RAVE users the possibility of using the platform to deposit, publish and share their trained RAVE models.

To promote this use, a special case of scenario 2.1, we plan to offer the RAVE 2 user community (around 200 people on an unofficial Discord) a new competition entitled: "RAVE model challenge". RAVE users will be invited to upload a RAVE model to the platform, enabling the sound timbre to be transferred in real time. Platform users will then be able to vote for the best model. This will not only enable new artistic resources to emerge on the platform, but also increase collector traffic, thus participating in a new form of collaborative artistic curation, based on principles similar to those of DAOs. The competition has three objectives: content creation, content curation and teaching DAO on the platform.

The objective for Scenario 2.2 is to extend the process initiated in the first phase of the use case and the general interest of the community with more dedicated licensing options, and the management of successive versions of repositories of the same work.

A number of factors will help to motivate targeted users: the presentation and publication in June-July 2024 of several articles in international conferences promoting the DAFNE+ platform to the Use case 2 communities, the availability in September 2024 of a new version of the platform, the launch of the DAO and the expected involvement of users in the proposals they will be able to submit and vote on, and the 2025 edition of the IRCAM Forum workshops which, like its previous edition, will be a major milestone for the realisation, public presentation and collective exchange of the processes launched for this second phase of use cases.

9.4.0 Scenario 2.1

- DAFNE+ competition: RAVE Model Challenge.

Following the example of the Generative Music Prize organised in 2023/2024, the RAVE Model Challenge covers the period 2024/2025 according to the following provisional timetable:

- September 2024 - November 2024: Submission portal opens
- November 2024 - February 2025 Public voting in the form of the purchase of NFT.

- February 2025: Closing of auction/vote and notification to the awardees
- March 2025: Award Ceremony during the IRCAM Forum workshops 2025

The community vote will be designed as a DAO proposal, enabling the users to familiarise themselves with the concepts of decentralised autonomous organisation.

9.4.1 Scenario 2.2

9.4.1.1 DAFNE+ webinar: Minting content on the platform 2

This webinar updated the minting process after Mumbai's move to Amoy. The video of the webinar will be available online and serve as a guided hand to understand the project, create an account and mint a content. Participants will also be invited to take part in the ongoing survey (see D5.1).

- Date: 28th of June 2024
- Duration: 60min.
- Link: <https://forum.ircam.fr/agenda/dafne-webinar-minting-content-on-the-platform-2/detail/>

9.4.1.2 DAFNE+ survey: User feedback gathering

The current online survey, for which preliminary results were given in D5.1, will continue until September 2024. It will be promoted at various upcoming events, conferences and webinars.

9.4.1.3 Early adopters

We plan to continue the work begun with the early adopters, in particular by putting online works whose electronic part is in line with the CC license. The plan is to actively involve them in the test phase of version 2 of the platform, starting in September 2025. An extra effort will be made to set up the DAO.

9.4.1.4 IRCAM Forum workshops 2025

Promotional actions will be carried out at major events, especially during the IRCAM Forum workshops 2025, where presentations, workshops and the RAVE challenge prize-giving ceremony will be held. An extra effort will be made to set up the DAO.

9.4.1.5 User support and community management

Support and communication efforts will be continued and centralised on the platform's discord channel. The IRCAM Forum's promotional materials will also be used: social networks, newsletter, events, etc. An extra effort will be made to set up the DAO.

9.4.1.6 Evaluation

At the end of the promotional phase for the second version of the platform, and as part of the IRCAM 2025 Forum workshops, an online survey will be published. The results will contribute to the overall evaluation of the platform.

9.4.2 Scenario 2.3

The implementation of Scenario 2.3 is suspended until real financial transactions are possible on the platform through its the integration of the mainnet network.

10 Use case 3 - Novel forms of artistic content exploitation

10.0 Introduction

During the first experimentation phase Use Case 3 (UC3) engaged with profiles of the community that included individuals from the Maker Movement community connected to the Fab Lab Network, Distributed Design Platform network, and the extended community of design practitioners, including students currently enrolled in Bachelor's and Master's degrees such as the [Master in Design for Emergent Futures](#) from Fab Lab Barcelona | IAAC. To better frame the profiles UC3 engaged with, it's relevant to highlight that most individuals in the network are self-employed entrepreneurs, freelancers, individuals reliant on research project grants, and students. The overall community includes established or semi-professional businesses (both employees and freelancers), people who work with art/design/craft as a side to external income, and creatives experimenting with innovation and emerging technologies as part of their educational journey.

In this regard, it's important to emphasise the need not to create a distinction between professionals and non-professionals as separate categories. Furthermore, it is important to underscore the commonalities in the profiles of all users in UC3. These include the workflow, in terms of how users create, contribute, redesign, remix, and share their designs, mainly through sharing platforms mostly used in the community, such as GitHub, GitLab, Wikifactory, Discord etc. Furthermore, it is crucial to comprehend the mentality of the UC3 community members. UC3 is connected to the maker movement, and with that comes a strong connection to the Open Source movement mentality, which advocates decentralisation, transparency, and unrestricted sharing of information

In relation to the mentioned workflow, it was possible to identify three types of user profiles and scenarios:

- **Repository/Component Creator:** This role pertains to the user responsible for creating a repository, whether it is locally stored or hosted on a third-party platform like Github or Gitlab.

- Repository/Component User: This role involves a user who creates a component for subsequent use or modification.
- Repository/Component Contributor: This role describes a user who has created a component and contributes bug fixes or modifications to either the original repository or a new version.

10.1 Scenario 3.1 - Repository/Component creator

Creator of a repository which is locally stored or hosted on a third-party library

10.1.0 Scenario description

A creative individual has prototyped and designed a project through an iterative process and has chosen to upload their project to an Open Source repository. The design includes a "How to" guide, comprising instructions on realising the design (e.g., a text file) and folders dedicated to various components of the overall design. These folders contain, for instance, 3D printing files for an enclosure, code for electronic components, and files for CNC-mill hardware. The repository, including the "How to" guide and folders, is hosted on Github (a third-party library), and the individual also wishes to host it on the DAFNE+ platform. For them, the simplest approach is to directly integrate their existing repository into the platform. Therefore, they will copy the URL of their repository and use the platform's content management tool to link the two.

Consequently, their repository remains hosted on Github but is directly linked to the version control and marketplace of DAFNE+. Utilising DAFNE+ adds value for the user, as they are open to additional verification of their work, receive extra recognition as the "original owner," and benefit from a transparent chain of adaptation and updates from other users, which are logged and visible on the platform (version control).

Observing remixed and new versions of their design, with local adaptations from other users, is of interest to the repository creator, as they perceive value in the enhancement of the original design idea.

10.1.1 User profiles

- Repository Creator
- Component Creator

10.1.2 Managed assets

- Repository: Folder/ Library containing a set of components and instructions
 - .md, json, .pdf, .txt; (Documentation includes free text, links, external sources etc.)
- Component A: File containing data to make component
 - CAD, OBJ, STL, STEP, DXF, SVG, Gcode, XTML etc.
- Component B: File containing code for e.g. electronic components

10.1.3 Promotional materials

Users may utilise media platforms such as Instagram, Shopify, or Big Cartel to sell components or entire designs. However, the DAFNE+ platform ideally provides an alternative to highly commercialised market websites that levy significant commissions on revenue. Within DAFNE+, the contribution margin is co-determined by the DAO, thereby benefiting the overall community. This presents a favourable alternative to profit-oriented online stores, where profits accrue to companies rather than the community. DAFNE+ user profiles and repositories should include space to link to these external websites. Users may also wish to enhance their profiles or repositories with images or videos showcasing their work.

10.1.4 Conditions for implementation

- Technically and easily accessible
- Low financial entry-level barrier
- Easy user engagement: interface, experience
- Transparency: Explicit social and environmental values (with an understanding of what fair and sustainable means)
- Trust
- Sustainability after the project's conclusion

10.1.5 User journeys

- 1) User enters the platform and learns about DAFNE+

- 2) The user creates a profile because the added value through DAFNE+ is clear. They would like to engage with alternative business models for added value and an additional source of income. They are interested in blockchain technology and how this could make a transparent chain of tracking changes and adaptations of designs. They are also interested in being part of a DAO, because they value community-centric governance for collective decision making and community profit investments.
- 3) The user decides to upload a repository they have created potentially on a third-party library
- 4) User will add a description of their project, possibly add images or videos from their project, and add links to external websites and platforms
- 5) The user will be able to review information about NFT's and Blockchain to better understand how that connects to their work, and how they can gain revenue. E.g. information about how to create a wallet/ metamask.
- 6) The user may browse through other content creator profiles to explore other projects. For this, it would be useful to have a browse page in which users can choose e.g. tags to find projects/ repositories related to #music, #digitalfabrication #cncmilling or similar
- 7) The user may also be interested in seeing geographically where other projects are to be able to collaborate locally on projects
- 8) The user may want to write directly to other users
- 9) The user may be interested in adding "interest" tags to their profile, so other users can identify their area of interest and expertise

10.2 Scenario 3.2 – Repository/Component user

User who mints component for further usage or adaptation

10.2.0 Scenario description

The user may fall into categories such as "professional," "semi-professional," or "hobbyist" and is keen on minting components or entire repositories to recreate projects (or parts thereof) in their local environment.

Their primary interest lies in browsing the DAFNE+ website to explore creations by others. They are eager to utilise tags or geolocation to discover specific projects aligned with their interests. The user embraces Open Source principles and possesses a fundamental understanding of their applications. Moreover, they are intrigued by the potential integration of blockchain and NFTs into their workflow. The user is likely to discover an inspiring project either through organic browsing or direct search, mint or download it, and employ its instructions for replication.

10.2.1 User profiles

- Repository User
- Component User

10.2.2 Managed assets

- Repository: Folder/ Library containing a set of components and instructions
 - .md, json, .pdf, .txt, (Documentation includes free text, links, external sources, etc.)
- Component A: File containing data to make component
 - CAD, OBJ, STL, STEP, DXF, SVG, Gcode, XTML etc.
- Component B: File containing code for e.g. electronic components

10.2.3 Promotional materials

The user may not own their own repository on the DAFNE+ platform. The user may be interested in linking to their social media or other external pages/website already used in the workflow, such as Github, Gitlab, Wikifactory or other open-source platforms.

10.2.4 Conditions for implementation

- Technically and easily accessible
- Low financial entry-level barrier
- Easy user engagement: interface, experience

- Transparency: Explicit social and environmental values (with an understanding of what fair and sustainable means)
- Trust
- Sustainability after the project's conclusion

10.2.5 User journeys

- 1) The user enters the DAFNE+ platform
- 2) The users browse through the platform to understand the vision and the added values that DAFNE+ offers
- 3) The user enters a section of the platform that showcases the different creative works of DAFNE+ users. The content is shown potentially randomly or by “latest to be added” and the user scrolls through them to explore what the DAFNE+ community is working on
- 4) The user is interested in finding a project to recreate
- 5) The user uses the search function to find projects that work with #digitalfabrication, which are #easy to replicate and use #circularmaterials
- 6) A page with different repositories from different users around the world is being shown, using the tags and an identification system
- 7) The user can further define their search by tags that define the quality of the work done. For e.g. some of the repositories created have earned badges from the DAFNE+ community for specifically well-made repositories, or for being great contributors
- 8) The user visits some of the repository creator profiles to learn more about them and their work
- 9) Based on the quality of the repository and the types of badges the repository creator has earned the user is choosing a repository to recreate
- 10) The user is minting/ downloading the repository and making it locally in their home/maker space or Fab Lab

10.3 Scenario 3.3 - Repository/Component contributor

User who has minted component and contributes with bug fix or adaptation, to original or new repository version

10.3.0 Scenario description

The user is a maker or designer with experience in creating projects and contributing to others'. They actively contribute to repositories or components and may also establish their own. The user is drawn to the DAFNE+ platform due to its added value. This includes transparent version control, facilitated by blockchain technology, and a secondary revenue model wherein they gain reputation and a form of monetary exchange for their contributions (further discussion is needed to clarify its relation to NFTs).

10.3.1 User profiles

- Repository Contributor
- Component Contributor

10.3.2 Managed assets

- Repository: Folder/ Library containing a set of components and instructions
 - .md, json, .pdf, .txt, (Documentation includes free text, links, external sources, etc.)
- Component A: File containing data to make component
 - CAD, OBJ, STL, STEP, DXF, SVG, Gcode, XTML
- Component B: File containing code for e.g. electronic components

10.3.3 Promotional materials

In addition to managing version control and potential reputation-based incentives, there are certain essential contents necessary for presenting and promoting assets. These include visual assets like images and videos showcasing the project, detailed written descriptions, step-by-step instructions, external links to related resources.

10.3.4 DAO related rules

- Technically and easily accessible
- Low financial entry-level barrier
- Easy user engagement: interface, experience
- Transparency: Explicit social and environmental values (with an understanding of what fair and sustainable means)
- Trust
- Sustainability after the project's conclusion

10.3.5 User journeys

- 1) The user is entering the DAFNE+ platform, being a regular user.
- 2) The user sees the latest added repositories
- 3) They potentially browse through those repositories to see if there is an interesting project to contribute to
- 4) The user reviews their notifications to see if their proposed updates and changes have been reviewed and accepted by other users and repository creators
- 5) The user has received a badge for being a contributor which is adding “valuable feedback” from x amount of other users. (The idea is that they receive a badge e.g. bronze, silver and gold after multiple users have verified the quality of their work)
- 6) The user has worked offline on some updates to another repository. They are now visiting the repository owner page to add their new contribution to the repository
- 7) The user is commenting on the repository, adding additional files and images from the alteration and update.

10.4 Implementation strategy

10.4.0 Early adopters

The early adopter strategy towards phase 2, will be developed based on the key information and insights collected during the first phase of Use Case Refinement (T2.3). Many interviewees during this phase expressed concerns about their lack of understanding of key concepts such as blockchain, NFTs, and DAOs connected to DAFNE+. Despite these concerns, there was a strong curiosity to learn more about these concepts and how to implement them in practice.

The next implementation strategy will investigate the conditions necessary for the platform to be easily accessible in terms of both technical complexity and financial entry-level challenges. This strategy will focus on introducing the concepts, from basic to more specific topics, and continue to engage users by testing the platform, providing support, and collecting feedback on personal projects. Additionally, the strategy will open discussions related to the DAO mechanism, which will be crucial for version 2 of the platform.

10.4.1 Ambassadors

The next phase will highlight the roles of the ambassadors chosen through the open call launched in April 2024, which was implemented as a strategy to ensure transparency and fairness in the selection process and to reach the diverse network's profiles within UC3.

The two chosen ambassadors are [Jorge Muñoz Zanón](#) and [Aiwen Yin](#). Their selection was based on their ability to engage with diverse target audiences through various activities. These activities include developing a research paper, participating in a podcast interview, attending events, and hosting workshops.

10.4.2 Promotion

The promotion strategy at Fab Lab Barcelona I IAAC will continue to be focused on engaging the global user community through online dissemination actions, while also supporting DAFNE+ project dissemination through offline event participation carried out by the ambassadors and Fab Lab Barcelona I IAAC coordinating with the consortium partners.

10.4.2.1 Future Talk Podcast: DAFNE+ Series

In June, the first episode of the Future Talk Podcast “DAFNE+ Series” will be launched. This series will feature special guests who have already been engaged with the project and can relate their expertise and practice to real case examples from the DAFNE+ project.

Future guests such as Aiwen Yin, have already been confirmed. Aiwen Yin’s episode will be as conclusion of the ambassador activities and will serve as a collective provocative reflection on the role and future learning experiences aimed at broadening the dialogue towards reimagining educational tools for decentralised caring social infrastructure.

- Date: From June 2024
- Duration: Around 40-60 minutes
- Link: To be Published

10.4.2.2 Web3Expressão - Oficinas criativas para um futuro digital

In April 2024, a collaboration with the [Goethe Institute of Lisbon](#) began, leading to the presentation of “[Web3Expressão - Oficinas criativas para um futuro digital](#)”. This program aims to introduce artists and creatives in Lisbon to the world of Web3 and new technologies. Fab Lab Barcelona | IAAC will collaborating with local expert [João Ribeiro](#) to lead the workshop on Ethical AI, sharing examples and projects created during the Creative Jam 2024.

- Date: July 9th, 2024
- Duration: 120 minutes
- Location: Lisbon

10.4.2.3 DAFNE+ Blockchain and NFT Partner Symposium

In March 2024, Fab Lab Barcelona | IAAC, in collaboration with the School of Digital Arts at Manchester University, began planning a two-hour DAFNE+ Blockchain and NFT Partner Symposium to be held during the

second week of July 2024. This event aims to invite consortium partners and interested users identified during the initial phase to present and engage in interdisciplinary dialogue. Through a collective sharing format, participants will discuss best practices and research related to DAFNE+ key concepts and topics, fostering collaboration and advancing scholarly understanding of the complex dynamics of NFTs and blockchain.

The symposium will conclude with an open discussion on DAO mechanisms and priorities, providing direct insights to our technical partners for the implementation of DAOs in the next phase of the platform. This event will also serve as an opportunity to gather feedback on formats for future events scheduled between October and December 2024.

- Date: 2nd week of July
- Duration: 120 minutes
- Link: To be Published

10.4.2.4 DAFNE+ Meet-up series

- Date: Between October - December 2024
- Duration: 60 minutes
- Link: To be Published

A three-part meetup series focusing on gamification, phygital NFTs, and tokenomics. These short series events aim to acquaint participants with the DAFNE+ project and platform, fostering engagement and curiosity with diverse topics relevant to the creative community.

Attendees will also gain a preliminary knowledge for the forthcoming Creative Jam in January 2025, laying the groundwork for deeper exploration during the international seminar.

10.4.2.5 Creative Jam 2025

The second edition of the Creative Jam, in collaboration with the School of Digital Arts (SODA) at Manchester University, will take place in January 2025. The methodology, strategy, and experts involved will directly result from the previous engagements' feedback during the past Creative Jam 2024 and the following activities

developed from both Use Cases. This international hybrid event will involve students from the first year of the Master in Design for Emergent Futures while including alumni from the previous year, who will take on various roles in tutoring and supporting different aspects with their peers of testing the platform and leading to the 2025 event.

10.4.3 User support and community management

Fab Lab Barcelona | IAAC will continue to provide user support and engage with existing and future users by fostering participation on the project's Discord channel. While recognising that each UC already has its distinct community on Discord before the initiation of the DAFNE+ project, the objective is to foster collective events to align all User Communities under one DAFNE+ Discord channel. This transition aims to cultivate a more cohesive ecosystem around the platform, promoting transdisciplinary collaboration among users interested in partner topics from different UCs. Furthermore, it guarantees that users from various communities receive uniform assistance and guidance from technical partners. These partners are equipped to tackle potential bugs in the platform and address specific issues, including legal and monetisation concerns.

To achieve community trust and improve user support and community management, our strategy involves inviting technical partners to participate and lead focus group discussions and other live sessions. This collaborative approach enables a reciprocal share of valuable insights into user needs and challenges, while redefining and improving specifications and supporting strategies for the next phase.

10.4.4 Evaluation

As part of a continuous monitoring and evaluation effort, UC3 will keep tracking qualitative feedback through blog posts, individual reflections, and one-on-one interviews with Jorge Muñoz Zanón, in the role of UC3 ambassador. These activities aim to continuously support technical partners by gathering feedback from early adopters regarding platform usage and interest.

The collected insights will keep adding to the conclusions and analysis report (D5.1) to improve the experience and facilitate necessary learning improvements for the development of the Creative Jam 2025 II edition. This feedback will also contribute to developing a less extractive methodology for users during the second experimentation phase.

11 User requirements for platform update

11.0 Introduction

Starting from the user requirements, technical specifications and architecture described in D2.1 the DAFNE+ Platform Applications were developed and integrated in the first version of the DAFNE+ Platform.

At the end of the integration phase, the first DAFNE+ Platform was officially released in November 2023 and was tested and evaluated within the first round of pilot.

Project partners were invited to test the platform before its public opening and provided feedback on its operation and interfaces. In particular, some of high priority comments were already taken into account in intermediate versions of the platform in order to improve for major events.

In addition, for each pilot and use case, end-users were involved during dedicated workshops for testing the overall platform and giving their feedback.

The feedback collected during the first validation phase allows to refine and consolidate the requirements for the improving of the DAFNE+ Platform, that will be updated and released in two additional major versions: intermediate version in September 2024 and in a final version by the end of the project.

This section will give a high-level description of the requirements and functionalities to be included in the next versions of the DAFNE+ Platform, in addition to what was reported in D2.1 and already planned. A detailed analysis and the final version of the requirements will be provided in D2.4 in December 2024.

11.1 Platform features

11.1.0 Asset management

The asset management features, mainly provided by the Content Management Tool, were extensively tested during the evaluation and some interesting feedback was collected.

Main feedback was related to some difficulties on the usage of the platform and in particular to the connection of the MetaMask plugin and accessing the related blockchain features. Furthermore, the importance of having the Content Management and the NFT Marketplace strictly connected was also highlighted.

In addition, the Organisation and Teams section was not tested enough due to its complexity.

No particular or blocking technical bugs or issues were reported.

In order to address the collected feedback, the Content Management Tool will implement the following features, in addition to those already planned for the second release:

- the possibility to **create NFT directly from the Content Management**
- **additional type of contents** (e.g., Work repository)
- **facilitation of the usage of the Content Management** (tutorials and tooltips)
- **revisioning of the Organisation and Teams section** (both in terms of UI and functionalities)

11.1.1 Asset publication

The asset publication features are mainly related to the NFT Marketplace that was probably the most tested section of the DAFNE+ Platform.

From Use Case 2 scenario, one of the main feedback items is related to the “possibility to **mint an NFT of the repository, including a validation phase by the user of the CC license**, with a predefined set of options.

In addition, as reported in the Content Management sub-section, a **new type of asset, the Work repository**, should be included. This new type should also include **additional information and metadata**, such as work title, composer name and work version, paving in this way the road for the **implementation of versioning system** in the version of the DAFNE+ Platform.

Furthermore, a **better visualisation of the digital asset within the Marketplace** was suggested, taking into consideration all the possible types of assets related to the different use cases.

Figure 3 below shows a possible mockup for the visualisation of work repository within the NFT Marketplace.

FIGURE 3: MOCKUP OF WORK REPOSITORY INTERFACE IN THE MARKETPLACE

Additional improvement could also include:

- Adding a markdown parser for including READ.ME files (low priority).
- Link to composer (work author in general): redirect to author profile
- Link to work presentation URL (optional)

Another important topic raised was the possibility of **providing insights on the quality of content in the form of badges, implementing a Reputation System**. In this way, “Users will be able to find trust-worthy and quality content” and “Creators will be able to attract a larger audience”.

A first implementation of the Reputation System will include **metrics and badges based on items**. This implementation will allow the Users to verify the quality of content (e.g., repository) in the form of badges giving them the possibility to find a simple way trust-worthy and high reputation contents in the catalogue. In this way, also creators will be able to attract a larger audience.

For this first implementation of the reputation system, a list of badges will be identified and for each of them the following aspects will be provided:

- Name (and image)
- Metric (how to calculate the badge)
- Description
- Value (the minimum number of actions for collecting the badge)

Additional mechanisms, for example based on creator reputation, can be investigated in the final stage of the project.

Further details about the first implementation of the Reputation System will be provided in D4.3 expected at M26 (August 2024).

Finally, the **licensing models should be revised**, including the possibility for a new user to **request the right to produce a new version of a specific content**, keeping at the same time the **ownership rights to the original creator**.

11.1.2 Tools

The DAFNE+ Platform provides an extensive list of tools on the Tools Catalogue accessible for the DAFNE+ users. No particular feedback (with exceptions such as RAVE) was collected about the usage of the Tools that will be released and improved for the second integration phase as originally planned.

11.1.3 Community management and DAO

The community management and the implementation of the DAO was not implemented in the first version of the DAFNE+ Platform and a dedicated component will be part of the intermediate release.

As described in section [5.1](#) in the first implementation of the DAO, a single community will be managed: the DAFNE+ Governance DAO.

This first DAO will be used as a testing community for implementing basic functionalities for DAO Management that will allow the possibility to manage the DAFNE+ Platform governance (business models, implementation, etc.)

Main features required for the DAO Management must at least include:

- **NFT Governance for DAFNE+ DAO**
- **Create, discuss, and vote DAO proposals.**

These features will be implemented leveraging on the DAFNE+ Blockchain Realm, exploiting the blockchain and smart contracts features for all the DAO mechanisms, ensuring transparency and security among DAO community for the DAFNE+ governance aspects. The first version of the DAFNE+ DAO system will be extended in the final stage of the project for supporting additional features such as the multiple choices for the implementation of the RAVE Model Challenge proposed by Use case 2 and presented in section 9.4.0.

11.1.4 Monitoring and evaluation

For the monitoring and the evaluation of the DAFNE+ Platform, as well as for the collection of some of the KPIs, a dedicated open-source web analytics platform was deployed and integrated with DAFNE+: Matomo [<https://matomo.org>].

Matomo supports the automatic collection of metrics that can help assess and optimise the validation and monitoring phase.

As described in D5.1, in the first validation of the platform Matomo was used for tracking the access and navigation within the different sections of the DAFNE+ Platform, and additional metrics were collected from aggregated historical data of the DAFNE+ Platform.

In the second phase of the project, **Matomo will be also used for tracking particular events** that can support the validation phase in an easiest way.

Matomo event tracking [[Implement event tracking with Matomo FAQ - Reports - Matomo Analytics Platform](#)] allows to setup configurable event for tracking specific KPIs.

A preliminary and not exhaustive list of events is reported in Section 6.1 of this document.

11.2 User experience

The following section reports some feedback related to the User Experience (UX) of the DAFNE+ Platform.

This feedback, together with technical ones, will be considered for the next releases of the platform, trying to improve both the UX and UI for facilitating the platform adoption.

11.2.0 User interfaces

In general, the comments about User Interfaces highlight the necessity to **have more coherent sections within the platform** itself and also compared to the DAFNE+ website.

Starting from the welcome page, it was suggested to include “**a tour of the platform with a small pop-up message to highlight features of the platform and how to get started**”. This tutorial can facilitate the first access and the usability of the platform features.

As already reported, the MetaMask plugin was mentioned several times during the evaluation phase. In terms of UI, it was suggested to **emphasise the MetaMask logo and its purpose** since “it is not well recognised by everyone”

The Content Management Tool and in particular the **Organisation and Teams** section needs a revision in **terms of colour and style** since it “brings confusion”.

In addition, it was suggested to have a “**more intuitive start by having the option to create My Team and then add people to the community and then create My Content to assign/collaborate with someone**”. In this version of Content Management, the entry point is the creation of contents.

Within NFT Marketplace section, some style and graphical revision was suggested. For example:

- tags and types of side borders in gradient should not appear and instead gradient must be full width
- Move filter option “sort items” below the search bar or next to it on the right.

In order to revise the UI of the DAFNE+ Platform, an analysis of the feedback will be conducted, and some **mock-up and style guidelines will be provided for the next implementation of the component’s frontend**.

In order to incentivise new users to join the platform and ease the registration process, **the access to the Marketplace and the FAQ/videos sections will be no longer reserved to registered users but will be made publicly available**.

11.2.1 Documentation

Main relevant feedback during the validation phase was related to the lack of intuitive functionality of the platform and above all on the use of MetaMask and the mechanisms linked to the blockchain. For this reason, the DAFNE+ Platform FAQ section will include additional technical **documentation and video tutorials** that can facilitate the accessibility to the main functionalities, including among others: **MetaMask Wallet connection, creation of contents, minting, buying and selling of NFT**.

11.2.2 User support

The DAFNE+ Platform includes a dedicated section for supporting the user during the navigation and usage of the platform itself: “FAQ and Chat” section.

In the current version of the platform, the “FAQ and Chat” section provides a series of guidelines and answers to common issues as well the possibility to contact the DAFNE+ project partners redirecting to the institutional website (<https://dafneplus.eu/contact/>).

In addition, a plugin for Discord DAFNE+ channel is embedded and in the same section. The chat plugin allows to communicate in the public Discord DAFNE+ channel both with other people and DAFNE+ consortium.

In the following versions of the DAFNE+ Platform, as defined during the requirements collection and confirmed by the first round of feedback collected, it is necessary to extend the support to the users including **wizards, tutorials and short videos** that can guide the user during the DAFNE+ Platform navigation, at least after the registration and first access.

Furthermore, more **information and instructions** (e.g., how to create and link a web3 wallet) **about blockchain technology** and how it is used into the Platform will be provided, including a clear description about the benefits that this technology can provide to the end-users.

Finally, together with the release of the first version of the DAO System, an **explanation about DAO concept** and how it can be used and exploited within the DAFNE+ ecosystem will be included.

12 Conclusions

The final version of the specification of use cases resulting from a process carried out during the second year of the DAFNE+ project has been presented. This specification prepares the implementation of the second phase use case pilots until the end of the project and the development of the next version of the DAFNE+ platform.

